

Improving the Performance of the Capriccio Method by Migrating to the Open-Source Programming Language Julia

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Nomenclature

Description	Symbol
Total energy of the coupled system with weighted energy contributions	E_H^{tot}
Number of FE nodes	n_n
Number of anchor points	n_{MS}
Number of FE elements	n_{el}
Number of FE nodes per element	n_{en}
Shape function of global node I	N_I
Vector of all positions of anchor points	\mathbf{r}^{MS}
Vector of all initial positions of anchor points	\mathbf{R}^{MS}
Position of single anchor point	\mathbf{r}_I^{MS}
Initial position of single anchor point	\mathbf{R}_I^{MS}
Vector of all positions of super-atoms that are tethered to anchor points	\mathbf{r}^{MD}
Position of single super-atom which is tethered to anchor point I	$\mathbf{r}_{J(I)}^{MD}$
Continuum displacement field	\mathbf{U}
Displacement field discretized at FE nodes	\mathbf{U}^h
Individual FE node displacement	\mathbf{U}_I
Vector of all anchor point displacements	\mathbf{W}
Individual anchor point displacement	\mathbf{W}_I
Lagrange multipliers	λ
Force on anchor points in deformed position	\mathbf{g}_r^{AP}
Force on anchor points in deformed position projected onto FE nodes	$\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_r^{AP}$
Force on anchor points in initial position	\mathbf{g}_R^{AP}
Force on anchor points in initial position projected onto FE nodes	$\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_R^{AP}$
Weighted finite element stiffness matrix	$\hat{\mathbf{K}}^c$
Weighted internal force vector of the continuum	$\hat{\mathbf{f}}^{int}$
Weighted external force vector of the continuum	$\hat{\mathbf{f}}^{ext}$
Individual spring stiffness	k_I
Diagonal matrix of spring stiffnesses	\mathbf{K}^{AP}
Spring stiffness matrix projected onto FE nodes	$\tilde{\mathbf{K}}^{AP}$
Coupling matrices	$\mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}, \mathbf{G}_{d\lambda}$

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Nowadays, engineering problems are usually treated by a continuum approach by means of the finite element method (FEM). Here, matter is considered to be distributed continuously throughout a body with its response to loads being modeled through differential equations. For mechanical problems, these are derived by combining the various balance equations with a constitutive material model. This is made possible by the assumption that the macroscopic behavior of a material is not influenced to a significant degree by the behavior of individual molecules or atoms, which is often the case for elastic and to some extent even plastic deformations. This approach, however, encounters its limits when processes taking place at the molecular level have to be taken into account explicitly, as is the case for cracks or when investigating the influence of nanoparticles. Here, a so-called multiscale modelling approach is required to connect particle-based considerations with continuum mechanics.

Although there already exist some simulation techniques for multiscale models, for example the Quasicontinuum [1] and the Arlequin [2] method, these have been developed primarily with crystalline materials in mind and are therefore not well suited to simulate polymers. For this reason, the Capriccio method, which builds upon the Arlequin method, has been developed. The core aim of the Capriccio method is to create a highly accurate simulation technique for fracturing in polymers by taking advantage of a multiscale partitioned domain simulation scheme.

Up until now, the Capriccio method has been developed with mostly the mathematical and physical formulations in mind. Yet, little attention has been directed towards creating a fast and efficient implementation of the mathematical foundations so far.

1.2 Aims and Outline of this Work

The aim of this thesis is to reevaluate the current state of the Capriccio method; with respect to both its mathematical foundations and its implementation as a computer program. To this end, a new point-wise coupling constraint is introduced, which promises faster execution and more accurate results while being conceptually simpler. Furthermore, a closer look at the weighting factor α , which has its origins in the Arlequin method, is taken, and a new approach of defining α using a partial differential equation is presented and discussed.

The Capriccio method is then implemented in the open-source programming language Julia. This implementation makes use of the point-wise coupling constraint and the newly introduced definition for α . It is then compared to the existing MATLAB implementation of the Capriccio method, both in terms of execution time and with respect to result accuracy, by running simulations on identical sample systems with nearly identical input parameters on both implementations. These results are then compared and discussed.

2 Improving the Capriccio Method

The Capriccio method, as discussed in [3] and [4], utilizes a staggered iteration scheme in which the molecular dynamics formulation and the finite element formulation of the mechanical problem are solved in alternating order. These are then coupled by introducing massless anchor points and modifying the classical FE and MD formulations in order to accommodate their force contributions. Here, a great portion of the development efforts of the Capriccio method lie in the accommodation of the anchor points within the finite element region.

The following discussions of the coupling constraint and the calculation of the alpha value are to be seen as an extension to the works by Pfaller [3] [4]. Therefore, citations to these sources are omitted in this chapter.

2.1 Coupling Constraint

At its core, the Capriccio method involves solving an optimization problem which is defined as the Lagrange function

$$L(\boldsymbol{\lambda}, \mathbf{U}, \mathbf{W}, \mathbf{r}^{MD}) = E_H^{tot}(\mathbf{U}, \mathbf{r}^{MD}) + b(\boldsymbol{\lambda}, \mathbf{U}, \mathbf{W}) + p(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{r}^{MD}), \quad (2.1)$$

with the total energy of the hybrid system

$$E_H^{tot}(\mathbf{U}, \mathbf{r}^{MD}) = \hat{E}_c^{tot}(\mathbf{U}) + \hat{E}_d^{tot}(\mathbf{r}^{MD}), \quad (2.2)$$

the individual energy contributions

$$\hat{E}_c^{tot}(\mathbf{U}) = \hat{E}_c^{int}(\mathbf{U}) - \hat{E}_c^{ext}(\mathbf{U}), \quad (2.3)$$

$$\hat{E}_d^{tot}(\mathbf{r}^{MD}) = \hat{E}_d^{int}(\mathbf{r}^{MD}) - \hat{E}_d^{ext}(\mathbf{r}^{MD}), \quad (2.4)$$

and the penalty term

$$p(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{r}^{MD}) = \sum_{I=1}^{n_{MS}} p_I(\mathbf{W}_I, \mathbf{r}_{J(I)}^{MD}) = \sum_{I=1}^{n_{MS}} \frac{1}{2} k_I \left| \mathbf{R}_I^{MS} + \mathbf{W}_I - \mathbf{r}_{J(I)}^{MD} \right|^2. \quad (2.5)$$

Here, $J(I)$ denotes the index of the molecular dynamics super-atom which is coupled to the anchor point I . In vector notation, this is denoted by an inverted hat:

$$\check{\mathbf{r}}^{MD} := \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}_{J(1)}^{MD} \\ \mathbf{r}_{J(2)}^{MD} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{r}_{J(n_{MS})}^{MD} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.6)$$

The optimization problem is solved when a saddle point of the Lagrange function L is obtained. The saddle point of (2.1) is obtained by taking the variations of L with respect to $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$, \mathbf{U} , \mathbf{W} , and \mathbf{r}^{MD} :

$$\begin{aligned}\delta_{\mathbf{U}}L &= \delta_{\mathbf{U}}\hat{E}_c^{tot} + \delta_{\mathbf{U}}b &= 0 & \quad \forall \delta\mathbf{U} \\ \delta_{\mathbf{W}}L &= \delta_{\mathbf{W}}b + \delta_{\mathbf{W}}p &= 0 & \quad \forall \delta\mathbf{W} \\ \delta_{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}L &= \delta_{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}b &= 0 & \quad \forall \delta\boldsymbol{\lambda} \\ \delta_{\mathbf{r}^{MD}}L &= \delta_{\mathbf{r}^{MD}}\hat{E}_d^{tot} + \delta_{\mathbf{r}^{MD}}p &= 0 & \quad \forall \delta\mathbf{r}^{MD}\end{aligned}\tag{2.7}$$

The partial derivative of the penalty term with respect to the anchor point displacements \mathbf{W} reads as follows:¹

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial \mathbf{W}} = \mathbf{K}^{AP}[\mathbf{R}^{MS} + \mathbf{W} - \hat{\mathbf{r}}^{MD}] =: -\mathbf{g}_r^{AP}\tag{2.8}$$

It represents the negative of the force experienced by the anchor points in their deformed position as denoted by

$$\mathbf{r}^{MS} := \mathbf{R}^{MS} + \mathbf{W}.\tag{2.9}$$

However, for the purposes of the finite element description of the continuum domain, formulations based on the forces acting on the anchor points as if they were in their initial position \mathbf{R}^{MS} are preferred:

$$\mathbf{g}_R^{AP} := \mathbf{K}^{AP}[\hat{\mathbf{r}}^{MD} - \mathbf{R}^{MS}] = \mathbf{g}_r^{AP} + \mathbf{K}^{AP}\mathbf{W}\tag{2.10}$$

The definitions of both anchor force vectors

$$\mathbf{g}_r^{AP} = \mathbf{K}^{AP}[\hat{\mathbf{r}}^{MD} - \mathbf{r}^{MS}] \text{ and}\tag{2.11}$$

$$\mathbf{g}_R^{AP} = \mathbf{K}^{AP}[\hat{\mathbf{r}}^{MD} - \mathbf{R}^{MS}]\tag{2.12}$$

lead to the usage of the subscript "r" in reference to \mathbf{r}^{MS} and the subscript "R" in reference to \mathbf{R}^{MS} to differentiate between these two. With this, (2.8) can be rewritten as

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial \mathbf{W}} = \mathbf{K}^{AP}\mathbf{W} - \mathbf{g}_R^{AP}.\tag{2.13}$$

For the continuum part of the staggered solution scheme, the particle positions \mathbf{r}^{MD} are held constant. Therefore, their variations $\delta\mathbf{r}^{MD}$ are not taken into account. (2.7) and (2.13) then result in the following system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} \hat{\mathbf{f}}^{int}(\mathbf{U}^h) + \mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}\boldsymbol{\lambda}^h &= \hat{\mathbf{f}}^{ext} \\ \mathbf{K}^{AP}\mathbf{W} + \mathbf{G}_{d\lambda}\boldsymbol{\lambda}^h &= \mathbf{g}_R^{AP} \\ \mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}^T\mathbf{U}^h + \mathbf{G}_{d\lambda}^T\mathbf{W} &= \mathbf{0} \end{cases}\tag{2.14}$$

The linear system of equations renders

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{K}}^c & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{G}_{c\lambda} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{K}^{AP} & \mathbf{G}_{d\lambda} \\ \mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}^T & \mathbf{G}_{d\lambda}^T & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}^h \\ \mathbf{W} \\ \boldsymbol{\lambda}^h \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{f}}^{ext} \\ \mathbf{g}_R^{AP} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}.\tag{2.15}$$

¹Partial derivatives and variations have the following relationship: $\delta_{\mathbf{x}}f(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\partial f(\mathbf{x})}{\partial \mathbf{x}}\delta\mathbf{x}$. It is thus possible to use partial derivatives instead of variations here.

In order to transfer information between the finite element and the molecular dynamics description of the mechanical problem, a coupling constraint needs to be formulated. In the original Capriccio method, an integral coupling constraint with respect to two displacement fields is used:

$$c = \|\mathbf{U} - \mathbf{W}^*\|^2 = B_1 \int_{\Omega^b} [\mathbf{U} - \mathbf{W}^*] \cdot [\mathbf{U} - \mathbf{W}^*] dV + B_2 \int_{\Omega^b} \frac{\partial[\mathbf{U} - \mathbf{W}^*]}{\partial \mathbf{X}} : \frac{\partial[\mathbf{U} - \mathbf{W}^*]}{\partial \mathbf{X}} dV \stackrel{!}{=} 0 \quad (2.16)$$

In (2.16), \mathbf{W}^* follows from a moving least square (MLS) approximation Π of the particle displacements as $\mathbf{W}^* = \Pi(\mathbf{W})$.

The Capriccio method, as implemented for this thesis, uses a different coupling constraint which takes direct advantage of the shape functions used by the finite element method. It asserts that the finite element displacement evaluated at the initial position of an anchor point should match the displacement of the given anchor point:

$$\mathbf{c}_I = \sum_{J=1}^{n_n} N_J(\mathbf{R}_I^{MS}) \mathbf{U}_J - \mathbf{W}_I \stackrel{!}{=} \mathbf{0} \quad (2.17)$$

The coupling constraint in terms of Lagrange multipliers $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ follows as

$$b(\boldsymbol{\lambda}, \mathbf{U}, \mathbf{W}) = \sum_{I=1}^{n_{MS}} \boldsymbol{\lambda}_I \cdot \mathbf{c}_I. \quad (2.18)$$

Here, $\delta_{\mathbf{U}} b$ renders

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{\mathbf{U}} b &= \sum_{K=1}^{n_n} \sum_{I=1}^{n_{MS}} \delta \mathbf{U}_K \cdot \mathbf{I} N_K(\mathbf{R}_I^{MS}) \cdot \boldsymbol{\lambda}_I \\ &= \sum_{e=1}^{n_{el}} \sum_{\eta=1}^{n_{en}} \sum_{I=1}^{n_{MS}} \delta \mathbf{U}^{e\eta} \cdot \mathbf{I} N_{\eta}^e(\boldsymbol{\xi}(\mathbf{R}_I^{MS})) \cdot \boldsymbol{\lambda}_I. \end{aligned} \quad (2.19)$$

In matrix notation it follows that

$$\delta_{\mathbf{U}} b = \delta \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{G}_{c\boldsymbol{\lambda}} \boldsymbol{\lambda}. \quad (2.20)$$

The second coupling matrix $\mathbf{G}_{d\boldsymbol{\lambda}}$ is then constructed as

$$\delta_{\mathbf{W}} b = \sum_{I=1}^{n_{MS}} -\delta \mathbf{W}_I \cdot \boldsymbol{\lambda}_I = -\delta \mathbf{W}^T \boldsymbol{\lambda} = \delta \mathbf{W}^T [-\mathbf{I}] \boldsymbol{\lambda} = \delta \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{G}_{d\boldsymbol{\lambda}} \boldsymbol{\lambda}, \quad (2.21)$$

resulting in

$$\mathbf{G}_{d\boldsymbol{\lambda}} = -\mathbf{I}. \quad (2.22)$$

This initially results in a system of equations with a significantly higher number of degrees of freedom compared to the system of equations arising from the integral coupling constraint (2.16) as the point-wise coupling constraint introduces Lagrange multipliers for each anchor point compared to only introducing Lagrange multipliers for each finite element node in the bridging domain with the MLS approximation. However, since $\mathbf{G}_{d\boldsymbol{\lambda}}$ reduces to the negative Identity Matrix $-\mathbf{I}$ due to the choice of the point-wise coupling constraint, the resulting system of equations can be manipulated in such a way that it is

only dependent on the nodal displacement vector \mathbf{U}^h . For the first step, inserting (2.22) into (2.14) results in

$$\hat{\mathbf{f}}^{int}(\mathbf{U}^h) + \mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}\boldsymbol{\lambda} = \hat{\mathbf{f}}^{ext}, \quad (2.23)$$

$$\mathbf{K}^{AP}\mathbf{W} - \boldsymbol{\lambda} = \mathbf{g}_R^{AP}, \text{ and} \quad (2.24)$$

$$\mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}^T\mathbf{U}^h - \mathbf{W} = \mathbf{0}. \quad (2.25)$$

The relationship

$$\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}^T\mathbf{U}^h \quad (2.26)$$

follows immediately from (2.25). (2.9) can therefore be rewritten as

$$\mathbf{r}^{MS} = \mathbf{R}^{MS} + \mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}^T\mathbf{U}^h. \quad (2.27)$$

Furthermore, inserting (2.26) into (2.24) renders

$$\mathbf{K}^{AP}\mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}^T\mathbf{U}^h - \boldsymbol{\lambda} = \mathbf{g}_R^{AP}, \quad (2.28)$$

which can now be solved for $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ and inserted into (2.23):

$$\hat{\mathbf{f}}^{int}(\mathbf{U}^h) + \mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}\mathbf{K}^{AP}\mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}^T\mathbf{U}^h - \mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}\mathbf{g}_R^{AP} = \hat{\mathbf{f}}^{ext} \quad (2.29)$$

Next,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{K}}^{AP} := \mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}\mathbf{K}^{AP}\mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}^T, \quad (2.30)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_r^{AP} := \mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}\mathbf{g}_r^{AP}, \text{ and} \quad (2.31)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_R^{AP} := \mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}\mathbf{g}_R^{AP} = \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_r^{AP} + \tilde{\mathbf{K}}^{AP}\mathbf{U}^h \quad (2.32)$$

are introduced as the projections of the anchor point stiffnesses and the anchor point forces onto the FE nodes. This now renders the system of equations

$$\hat{\mathbf{f}}^{int}(\mathbf{U}^h) + \tilde{\mathbf{K}}^{AP}\mathbf{U}^h = \hat{\mathbf{f}}^{ext} + \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_R^{AP} \quad (2.33)$$

where \mathbf{U}^h is the only unknown quantity.² For the linear system of equations this can further be simplified to

$$\left[\hat{\mathbf{K}}^c + \tilde{\mathbf{K}}^{AP} \right] \mathbf{U}^h = \hat{\mathbf{f}}^{ext} + \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_R^{AP}. \quad (2.34)$$

This formulation can now be used to solve for \mathbf{U}^h using a Newton-Raphson iteration scheme. Furthermore, (2.34) is comparatively easy to append to an existing finite element simulation framework, as $\tilde{\mathbf{K}}^{AP}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_R^{AP}$ can be interpreted as additional contributions to the finite element stiffness matrix and to the external load vector. It has therefore the same structure as the system of equations used in a conventional FE simulation. Crucially, the size and number of non-zero entries in the coupled system matrix $\hat{\mathbf{K}}^c + \tilde{\mathbf{K}}^{AP}$ are the same as the FE stiffness Matrix $\hat{\mathbf{K}}^c$, and are therefore independent of the number of elements in the bridging domain and the number of anchor points. This is because $\tilde{\mathbf{K}}^{AP}$ is simply a projection of the anchor point stiffnesses onto the FE nodes. It still has to be shown whether the coupled system matrix is positive semi-definite, as this could allow for faster algorithms to be used when solving the linear system of equations.

²While it might look like this could further be simplified by using (2.32), one has to keep in mind that unlike \mathbf{g}_R^{AP} , $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_R^{AP}$ is a function of \mathbf{W} , and in extension a function of \mathbf{U}^h , cf. (2.8). This would thus be counterproductive.

Coupling matrix assembly

In general, the coupling matrix $\mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}$ is assembled according to (2.19). This results in a $(n_c^{dof} \times n_d^{dof})$ block matrix with $(n_n \times n_{MS})$ number of blocks. The individual blocks have size $(n \times n)$, where n is the dimensionality of the system. With this, the block matrix representation of $\mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}$ reads as

$$\mathbf{G}_{c\lambda} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{(n \times n)} N_1(\mathbf{R}_1^{MS}) & \cdots & \mathbf{I}_{(n \times n)} N_1(\mathbf{R}_{n_{MS}}^{MS}) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{I}_{(n \times n)} N_{n_n}(\mathbf{R}_1^{MS}) & \cdots & \mathbf{I}_{(n \times n)} N_{n_n}(\mathbf{R}_{n_{MS}}^{MS}) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.35)$$

$N_I(\mathbf{R}_J^{MS})$ is only non-zero if node I is part of the element that \mathbf{R}_J^{MS} resides in. The entries for all other nodes therefore vanish. As an example, consider the finite element grid as depicted in Figure 2.1. The corresponding assembled coupling matrix is shown in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.1: 2-dimensional example of a finite element grid with four anchor points.

Each column in the block matrix represents one anchor point while the rows represent the individual finite element nodes. Every column has exactly n_{el} entries, with n_{el} being the number of nodes per element.

	\mathbf{R}_1^{MS}	\mathbf{R}_2^{MS}	\mathbf{R}_3^{MS}	\mathbf{R}_4^{MS}
N_1				
N_2	$N_{21} \quad 0$ $0 \quad N_{21}$	$N_{22} \quad 0$ $0 \quad N_{22}$		
N_3	$N_{31} \quad 0$ $0 \quad N_{31}$	$N_{32} \quad 0$ $0 \quad N_{32}$		
N_4			$N_{43} \quad 0$ $0 \quad N_{43}$	
N_5	$N_{51} \quad 0$ $0 \quad N_{51}$	$N_{52} \quad 0$ $0 \quad N_{52}$	$N_{53} \quad 0$ $0 \quad N_{53}$	$N_{54} \quad 0$ $0 \quad N_{54}$
N_6	$N_{61} \quad 0$ $0 \quad N_{61}$	$N_{62} \quad 0$ $0 \quad N_{62}$		$N_{64} \quad 0$ $0 \quad N_{64}$
N_7			$N_{73} \quad 0$ $0 \quad N_{73}$	
N_8			$N_{83} \quad 0$ $0 \quad N_{83}$	$N_{84} \quad 0$ $0 \quad N_{84}$
N_9				$N_{94} \quad 0$ $0 \quad N_{94}$

Figure 2.2: Assembled coupling matrix for the system set-up in Figure 2.1. For visual clarity, the abbreviation $N_{IJ} := N_I(\mathbf{R}_J^{MS})$ is used.

Staggered solution

To accommodate the staggered iteration scheme, slight modifications to (2.27) and (2.34) have to be made. Specifically, the iteration number i has to be included. Additionally, the anchor point forces are commonly time-averaged:^{3 4}

$$\mathbf{r}_{(i)}^{MS} = \mathbf{R}^{MS} + \mathbf{G}_{c\lambda}^T \mathbf{U}_{(i-1)}^h, \quad (2.36)$$

$$\left[\hat{\mathbf{K}}^c + \tilde{\mathbf{K}}^{AP} \right] \mathbf{U}_{(i)}^h = \hat{\mathbf{f}}_c^{ext} + \langle \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_R^{AP} \rangle_{(i)}^{\mathcal{T}}. \quad (2.37)$$

Here, $\mathbf{U}_{(0)}^h$ denotes the initial deformation and is typically set to $\mathbf{0}$. The time-averaged anchor forces $\langle \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_R^{AP} \rangle_{(i)}^{\mathcal{T}}$ can be calculated in one of multiple ways. One approach is to record the time-averaged position of the anchored atoms:

$$\langle \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_R^{AP} \rangle_{(i)}^{\mathcal{T}} = \mathbf{G}_{c\lambda} \mathbf{K}^{AP} [\langle \tilde{\mathbf{r}}^{MD} \rangle_{(i)}^{\mathcal{T}} - \mathbf{R}^{MS}]. \quad (2.38)$$

³Because the anchor point positions do not appear in (2.37), it is not necessary to differentiate between their positions before and after the FE step as is done in [3] and [4]. Therefore, for the formulations presented here, $\mathbf{r}_{(i)}^{MS}$ simply denotes the anchor point positions used for the MD calculation in step i while \mathbf{R}^{MS} denotes the reference positions of the anchor points. Consequently, \mathbf{R}^{MS} is not updated during the iteration procedure.

⁴The average over time of any quantity $A(t)$ is defined as $\langle A \rangle^{\mathcal{T}} := \frac{1}{\delta t} \int_{t_0}^{t_0+\delta t} A(\tau) d\tau$.

However, due to implementation restrictions, the slightly less elegant approach

$$\langle \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_R^{AP} \rangle_{(i)}^{\mathcal{T}} = \mathbf{G}_{e\lambda} \langle \mathbf{g}_r^{AP} \rangle_{(i)}^{\mathcal{T}} + \tilde{\mathbf{K}}^{AP} \mathbf{U}_{(i-1)}^h \quad (2.39)$$

is instead used for the implementation presented in this thesis. The overall staggered iteration scheme of the Capriccio method is now as follows:

1. For each iteration number $i = 1, \dots, n$, repeat steps 2-5.
2. Update the anchor point positions $\mathbf{r}_{(i)}^{MS}$ according to (2.36).
3. Run the MD simulation with fixed anchor point positions $\mathbf{r}_{(i)}^{MS}$.

Outputs either the time-averaged position of the anchored atoms $\langle \tilde{\mathbf{r}}^{MD} \rangle_{(i)}^{\mathcal{T}}$ or the time-averaged forces acting on the anchor points in their displaced position $\langle \mathbf{g}_r^{AP} \rangle_{(i)}^{\mathcal{T}}$.

4. Project the time-averaged anchor forces onto FE nodes using (2.38) or (2.39).
5. Calculate the nodal displacements $\mathbf{U}_{(i)}^h$ according to (2.37).

Here, n is the total number of MD-FE iterations.

2.2 Alpha Calculation

The system set-up of the Capriccio method is depicted in Figure 2.3: The continuum domain Ω^c and the particle domain Ω^d are coupled via a bridging domain Ω^b with the weighting factor $\alpha(\xi)$, which is used to smoothly blend between the energy contributions from the continuum domain and the energy contributions from the particle domain. The weighting factor may be chosen as a constant, linear, or cubic function. Pfaller [3] lists

$$\alpha(\xi) = \frac{1}{2}, \quad (2.40)$$

$$\alpha(\xi) = 1 - \frac{\xi - \xi_a}{\xi_b - \xi_a}, \text{ and} \quad (2.41)$$

$$\alpha(\xi) = \frac{-[\xi - \xi_b]^2 [2\xi - 3\xi_a + \xi_b]}{[\xi_a - \xi_b]^3} \quad (2.42)$$

as possible choices for the weighting function, where ξ_a and ξ_b denote the value of ξ at the interface between the pure continuum and the bridging domain $\partial\Omega^c \cap \partial\Omega^b$ and between the pure particle domain and the bridging domain $\partial\Omega^d \cap \partial\Omega^b$, respectively.

Figure 2.3: Spatial coupling set-up of the Arlequin method with weighting factor α [3].

In the one-dimensional case, the calculation of α is well-defined as ξ is inherently a scalar value. However, as the calculation of α relies on ξ being a scalar value, the correct calculation of α becomes ambiguous for problems in two or three dimensions. Crucially, the exact shape of the boundary region now has to be taken into account. Therefore, a definition of α which is compatible with higher-dimensional problems is needed.

A first step towards defining α for higher-dimensional problems is to reinterpret ξ not as a unitful measure of distance but rather as a unitless quantity which is a function of the material position vector \mathbf{X} such that it varies between ξ_a and ξ_b according to its distance to either domain. This allows for ξ_a and ξ_b to be chosen arbitrarily. Therefore, they will from here on be defined as $\xi_a := 1$ and $\xi_b := 0$ without loss of generality. This reduces (2.41) and (2.42) to:

$$\alpha(\xi) = \xi \quad (2.43)$$

$$\alpha(\xi) = \xi^2[2\xi - 3] \quad (2.44)$$

In the one-dimensional case, $\xi(X) = \frac{X - X^{db}}{X^{cb} - X^{db}}$ is a linear function in X , where X is the material position, X^{db} is the material position at the boundary between the pure particle and the bridging domain, and X^{cb} is the material position at the boundary between the pure continuum and the bridging domain.

In higher dimensions, $\xi(\mathbf{X})$ should have no local extrema within the boundary domain Ω^b . One possible way of satisfying this condition is to assert that ξ should be a harmonic function, i.e., that its Laplacian should be 0 for all \mathbf{X} . This results in a differential equation

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Find } \xi \in C^2(\Omega^b) \text{ s.t.} \\ \Delta \xi = 0 \text{ in } \Omega^b, \\ \xi = 1 \text{ on } \Gamma_D^{cb}, \\ \xi = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma_D^{db}, \text{ and} \\ \nabla \xi \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma_N, \end{array} \right. \quad (2.45)$$

where $\Gamma_D^{cb} := \partial\Omega^c \cap \partial\Omega^b$ is the boundary between the pure continuum and the bridging domain, and $\Gamma_D^{db} := \partial\Omega^d \cap \partial\Omega^b$ is the boundary between the pure particle and the bridging domain. Furthermore, $\Gamma_N := \partial\Omega^b \setminus (\partial\Omega^c \cup \partial\Omega^d)$ is the boundary of the bridging domain, which connects to neither the pure continuum nor pure particle domain. These boundaries are depicted in Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4: Boundary regions used for the differential equation.

It should be noted, that the definition of $\xi(\mathbf{X})$ as presented in this thesis is arbitrary. There are likely other valid definitions that produce similar or better results. It should therefore be validated that the result obtained from this definition is within expectation on a case-by-case basis.

Analytical solutions

Closed-form analytical solutions for (2.45) can only be obtained for a small subset of possible bridging domains with simple geometric shapes. While the implementation of the Capriccio method uses the finite element method as a numerical approach to solve for $\xi(\mathbf{X})$, analytical solutions still provide valuable insight into the expected behavior of the scalar field ξ .

In the case of a cuboid bridging domain, where the continuum and particle boundaries are in opposition, a solution which matches the one-dimensional case closely can be obtained. For the bridging domain as depicted in Figure 2.6, this solution is linear in Y :

$$\xi(Y) = \frac{Y - Y^{db}}{Y^{cb} - Y^{db}} \quad (2.46)$$

In the case of a hollow cylindrical bridging domain, a solution can be obtained by making use of a cylindrical coordinate system. For the bridging domain depicted in Figure 2.7, the solution is a logarithmic function of the radius R :

$$\xi(R) = \frac{\ln(R) - \ln(R^{db})}{\ln(R^{cb}) - \ln(R^{db})} \quad (2.47)$$

This can be verified with the equation for the Laplace-operator for a cylindrical coordinate system

$$\Delta\xi = \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial\xi}{\partial R} + \frac{\partial^2\xi}{\partial R^2} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{R^2} \frac{\partial^2\xi}{\partial\varphi^2}}_{=0} + \underbrace{\frac{\partial^2\xi}{\partial Z^2}}_{=0} \quad (2.48)$$

and the partial derivatives of ξ with respect to R

$$\frac{\partial\xi}{\partial R} = \frac{1}{R[R^{cb} - R^{db}]} \quad \text{and} \quad (2.49)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2\xi}{\partial R^2} = \frac{-1}{R^2[R^{cb} - R^{db}]} \quad (2.50)$$

If the bridging domain is a hollow sphere, a solution can be obtained by making use of a spherical coordinate system. For the bridging domain depicted in Figure 2.8, the solution is a fractional function of the radius ρ :

$$\xi(\rho) = \frac{\rho^{cb} \rho - \rho^{db}}{\rho \rho^{cb} - \rho^{db}} \quad (2.51)$$

This can be verified with the equation for the Laplace-operator for a spherical coordinate system

$$\Delta\xi = \frac{2}{\rho} \frac{\partial\xi}{\partial\rho} + \frac{\partial^2\xi}{\partial\rho^2} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial^2\xi}{\partial\theta^2}}_{=0} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{\rho^2 \tan\theta} \frac{\partial\xi}{\partial\theta}}_{=0} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{\rho^2 \sin^2\theta} \frac{\partial^2\xi}{\partial\varphi^2}}_{=0} \quad (2.52)$$

and the partial derivatives of ξ with respect to ρ

$$\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \rho} = \frac{\rho^{cb} \rho^{db}}{\rho^2 [\rho^{cb} - \rho^{db}]} \text{ and} \quad (2.53)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial \rho^2} = \frac{-2\rho^{cb} \rho^{db}}{\rho^3 [\rho^{cb} - \rho^{db}]}. \quad (2.54)$$

Figure 2.5 plots the solutions obtained above for various bridging domain sizes. The gray dashed lines for the cylindrical and spherical boundary serve as a reference to a linear function with the same values at the boundaries. Ideally, all solutions for ξ would be linear in their respective coordinate. However, this is only the case for the cuboid bridging domain. The cylindrical and the spherical bridging domain both show non-linearities in the graph of their ξ -function; this is likely caused by the difference in surface area between the continuum and the particle boundary. Notably, these non-linearities are most pronounced for bridging domains that are significantly larger than the particle domain. However, it doesn't seem like this has a significant effect on the overall linearity of ξ for practical purposes, as the relative size of the bridging domain is typically quite small.

Figure 2.5: Analytical solutions of (2.45) for the cuboid, hollow cylinder and hollow sphere bridging domains for a selection of relative sizes. The gray dashed lines for the cylindrical and spherical boundary serve as a reference to a linear function with the same values at the boundaries.

Figure 2.6: Example of a cuboid boundary domain. The face shaded in blue represents the particle system boundary Γ_D^{db} with the red face representing the continuum boundary Γ_D^{cb} . Furthermore, the coordinates Y^{cb} and Y^{db} denote the positions of the boundaries along the Y -axis respectively. The other faces shaded in gray border neither the particle nor the continuum domain. They are therefore part of the Neumann boundary Γ_N .

Figure 2.7: Example of a hollow cylindrical boundary domain. The area shaded in blue represents the particle system boundary Γ_D^{db} with the red area representing the continuum boundary Γ_D^{cb} . Furthermore, the radii R^{cb} and R^{db} denote the respective sizes of the boundaries. The caps of the cylinder are shaded in gray and border neither the particle nor the continuum domain. They are therefore part of the Neumann boundary Γ_N .

Figure 2.8: Example of a hollow spherical boundary domain. The area shaded in blue represents the particle system boundary Γ_D^{db} with the red area representing the continuum boundary Γ_D^{cb} . Furthermore, the radii ρ^{cb} and ρ^{db} denote the respective sizes of the boundaries.

Numerical solution

In most cases, there exists no analytical solution to the differential equation (2.45). Instead, numerical methods, such as the finite element method, can be utilized to find approximate solutions. In order to solve (2.45) with the finite element method, the weak form of this differential equation is needed. To this end, the set of all admissible variations of ξ

$$\mathcal{X} := \left\{ \delta\xi \in H^1(\Omega^b) : \delta\xi = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma_D^{cb} \cup \Gamma_D^{db} \right\} \quad (2.55)$$

is introduced. After multiplying by $\delta\xi$ and integrating, the equation can be manipulated in the following way:

$$\int_{\Omega^b} \delta\xi \operatorname{div}(\nabla\xi) dv = 0 \quad \forall \delta\xi \in \mathcal{X} \quad (2.56)$$

$$\int_{\Omega^b} \operatorname{div}(\delta\xi \nabla\xi) dv - \int_{\Omega^b} \nabla\delta\xi \cdot \nabla\xi dv = 0 \quad \forall \delta\xi \in \mathcal{X} \quad (2.57)$$

$$\underbrace{\int_{\partial\Omega^b} \delta\xi \nabla\xi \cdot \mathbf{n} da}_{=0} - \int_{\Omega^b} \nabla\delta\xi \cdot \nabla\xi dv = 0 \quad \forall \delta\xi \in \mathcal{X} \quad (2.58)$$

The weak form of (2.45) then renders

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Find } \xi \in H^1(\Omega^b) \text{ with } \xi = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma_D^{db}, \text{ and } \xi = 1 \text{ on } \Gamma_D^{cb} \text{ s.th.} \\ \int_{\Omega^b} \nabla\delta\xi \cdot \nabla\xi dv = 0 \quad \forall \delta\xi \in \mathcal{X} \end{array} \right. \quad (2.59)$$

By expressing $\delta\xi$ and ξ using shape functions,

$$\xi := \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\xi}^e = \begin{bmatrix} N_1^e & N_2^e & \dots & N_{n_{en}}^e \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \xi_1^e \\ \xi_2^e \\ \vdots \\ \xi_{n_{en}}^e \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad (2.60)$$

$$\delta\xi := \mathbf{H}\delta\boldsymbol{\xi}^e = \begin{bmatrix} N_1^e & N_2^e & \dots & N_{n_{en}}^e \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \delta\xi_1^e \\ \delta\xi_2^e \\ \vdots \\ \delta\xi_{n_{en}}^e \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.61)$$

(2.59) can be rewritten as

$$\delta\boldsymbol{\xi}^{eT} \int_{\Omega^e} \nabla\mathbf{H}^T \nabla\mathbf{H} dv \boldsymbol{\xi}^e, \quad (2.62)$$

which then leads to the corresponding element stiffness matrix

$$\mathbf{K}^e = \int_{\Omega^e} \nabla\mathbf{H}^T \nabla\mathbf{H} dv. \quad (2.63)$$

Now the assembled global stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} , the discretized ξ vector $\boldsymbol{\xi}^h$, and the right-hand side \mathbf{r} can be split into sub-vectors and sub-matrices referring to degrees of freedom with prescribed (subscript "p") and unknown values for ξ (subscript "u"):

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{pp} & \mathbf{K}_{pu} \\ \mathbf{K}_{up} & \mathbf{K}_{uu} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\xi}_p^h \\ \boldsymbol{\xi}_u^h \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}_p^{rec} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.64)$$

Here, the right-hand side contains only the reaction "forces" \mathbf{r}_p^{rec} for the nodes on the Dirichlet boundary as there are no prescribed "forces" acting on the domain. The bottom row of (2.64) now reads

$$\mathbf{K}_{up}\boldsymbol{\xi}_p^h + \mathbf{K}_{uu}\boldsymbol{\xi}_u^h = \mathbf{0}, \quad (2.65)$$

which immediately results in

$$\boldsymbol{\xi}_u^h = -\mathbf{K}_{uu}^{-1}\mathbf{K}_{up}\boldsymbol{\xi}_p^h. \quad (2.66)$$

While \mathbf{r}_p^{rec} may be calculated from the top row of (2.64), it has no significance for the calculation of α and its calculation can therefore be omitted. With this approach, it is possible to use the same discretization as used for the continuum description of the mechanical problem. Conceptually, this can be interpreted as a simplified stationary heat equation where the boundaries are held at a constant temperature 1 or 0. It can therefore be implemented similarly. As ξ is formulated in terms of the material position vector \mathbf{X} , it is sufficient to calculate the nodal values of ξ once at the start of the simulation. Then, the values of ξ at any given quadrature point can be calculated using the shape functions evaluated at the given location

$$\xi(\mathbf{X}) = \sum_{\eta=1}^{n_{en}} N_{\eta}^e(\mathbf{X})\xi_{\eta}^e. \quad (2.67)$$

Figure 2.9 depicts the solution for the local coordinate field ξ for the example of a square boundary domain solved using the finite element method, with Figure 2.10 showing

the discretization used for the calculation. In regions far away from the corners, ξ is approximately linear in \mathbf{X} . However, in regions near the corners of the bridging domain, significant non-linearities can be observed: In those regions, the value of ξ is more similar to the analytical solution of the cylindrical bridging domain.

Figure 2.9: Example of local coordinate ξ in a 2-dimensional, hollow, square boundary domain. The outside edges are set to a constant value of 1 while the inside edges are set to 0. Isolines are drawn for 10 equally spaced values of ξ .

Figure 2.10: Discretization used for the numerical example depicted in Figure 2.9.

3 Implementation Details

The following chapter discusses some key details regarding the implementation of the Capriccio method in Julia with a focus on parallel execution.

3.1 Parallel Execution

As the Julia implementation is intended to be run on a high performance computing cluster with a large amount of cores, special considerations have to be taken into account in order to take full advantage of the available computing power. On high performance clusters, the message passing interface (MPI) is a commonly used tool for large scale parallel execution of programs. MPI works by launching the same program on multiple processors simultaneously. While these programs run for the most part independently of each other, they can use special functions outlined by the MPI specification to communicate with each other. The molecular dynamics code LAMMPS, for example, which both Capriccio implementations currently use to perform the MD part of the simulation, uses a spacial partitioning scheme, where each atom gets assigned to a processor according to its position in space. During the course of the simulation, the atoms migrate between the processors as they leave the domain of one processor and enter the domain of another. Furthermore, atoms that are near the boundaries of these domains are communicated to neighboring processors as so-called ghost atoms such that they can interact with atoms outside their respective domain.

Although MPI is fundamentally an API specification for the C Programming language, it is still possible to leverage its functionality through the MPI.jl wrapper library. However, the implementation of the finite element method used for the Capriccio implementation presented in this thesis does not take much advantage of the parallel capabilities of MPI yet, as the partitioning schemes and algorithms associated with large scale parallel FEM code are very complex and challenging to implement. It is therefore outside the scope of this thesis to implement this functionality. Instead, each processor independently assembles the linear system of equations (2.37), which results in a lot of duplicate work being done. This also means that each processor has its own full copy of the FE system stored in memory, which results in significantly higher memory usage than normally necessary. Nevertheless, the necessary means of implementing a proper large scale parallel FEM code are present through MPI.jl, which makes it possible to address these shortcomings in future improvements to the Capriccio-Julia implementation.

A notable exception to this lack of parallel computing is the solving phase of the linear system of equations. This step is handled by MUMPS, which is a massively parallel solver of linear equations.

3.2 Communication with LAMMPS

The Capriccio method in its current state utilizes a staggered solution scheme which alternates between finite element and molecular dynamics simulation steps. As it takes

Table 3.1: Methods exposed by LAMMPS.jl with a short description each.

method	description
<code>LMP()</code>	Initializes a LAMMPS instance
<code>command()</code>	Sends a command to a LAMMPS instance
<code>gather()</code>	Collects per atom data, such as forces, from a LAMMPS instance
<code>scatter!()</code>	Sends per atom data, such as positions, to a LAMMPS instance

a considerable amount of know-how and resources to write a performant molecular dynamics implementation, the widely used MD framework LAMMPS is utilized as the backbone of the molecular dynamics simulation [5]. The MD simulation takes the anchor point displacements resulting from the FE step as an input and produces forces on these anchor points as the output. These are in turn used at the finite element iteration step to calculate new anchor point displacements.

From this simulation set-up arises the need to communicate the anchor point displacements and anchor forces between the finite element and the molecular dynamics framework in both directions. Furthermore, it is necessary to trigger the subsequent iteration step at the end of both the finite element and the molecular dynamics simulation.

The general simulation procedure of the MATLAB implementation of the Capriccio method [6] is depicted in Figure 3.1. Here, MATLAB communicates with LAMMPS through operating system commands and a set of files containing information about anchor point displacements, anchor forces, and the current iteration step. The message passing interface (MPI), which enables parallelism across multiple cores and nodes, is only used for the molecular dynamics part of the simulation. As a result, LAMMPS is restarted at the beginning of each molecular dynamics iteration. This introduces significant overhead, as the atoms, bonds, and pairs as well as their interactions have to be redefined at every restart. Variable, compute, fix, thermo, and dump commands have to be reissued as well. Repeatedly reading and writing files is also detrimental to the performance of the simulation. This introduces avoidable complexity in the program which has to manage these temporary files.

The Julia implementation of the Capriccio method takes a different approach to communicating with LAMMPS. Instead of using files and operating system commands, it takes advantage of Julia’s excellent interoperability with the C programming language by directly communicating with LAMMPS through its C library interface. The Julia wrapper library LAMMPS.jl is used for this purpose, as it provides higher level abstractions to this library interface [7]. LAMMPS.jl exposes the methods `LMP()`, `command()`, `gather()`, and `scatter!()`, amongst others, which are outlined with respect to their functionality in Table 3.1. Here, `gather()` is used to retrieve the time averaged forces on the anchor points after a MD run while `scatter!()` is used to set the updated anchor point positions after a FE run.

This results in a considerably less complicated set-up for the general simulation procedure, which is depicted in Figure 3.2. Comparing this to the previous flow diagram in Figure 3.1, it becomes apparent that the overall simulation procedure has reduced significantly in complexity due to the elimination of read and write operations to temporary files.

Figure 3.1: Conceptual flow diagram of the MATLAB Capriccio implementation [6].

Figure 3.2: Conceptual flow diagram of the Julia Capriccio implementation.

4 Working Environment

The following sections outline the hardware and software used to run the simulation and to analyze the results.

Fritz

Fritz is a high performance, parallel CPU cluster located at the *Regional Computing Center Erlangen* (RRZE). In the context of this thesis, one computing node with two Xeon Platinum 8360Y "Ice Lake" chips (36 cores per chip) was used.

Julia

Julia is a high-level, high-performance programming language designed for technical computing, with an emphasis on numerical and scientific applications. [8]

This software serves as the backbone of the implementation of the Capriccio method presented in this thesis.

Ferrite.jl

Ferrite.jl is a finite element toolbox that provides functionalities to implement finite element analysis in Julia. It facilitates the distribution of degrees of freedom, the definition of Dirichlet boundary conditions, and the evaluation of functions and derivatives in the finite element space. Furthermore, it has the capability of exporting grids and solutions to the .vtu file format. [9]

Ferrite was used to implement the finite element simulation step used by the Capriccio method.

Makie.jl

Makie.jl is a data visualization ecosystem for the Julia programming language. It was used to create some of the plots presented in this thesis. [10]

MPI.jl

MPI.jl is a basic Julia wrapper for the portable message passing system *message passing interface* (MPI). This package was used to enable high-performance parallel routines within Julia and LAMMPS across multiple processors and nodes. [11] [12]

LAMMPS.jl

LAMMPS.jl is a Julia wrapper for the LAMMPS library interface. This package was used to allow for efficient communication between Julia and LAMMPS. [7]

MUMPS.jl

MUMPS.jl is a Julia wrapper for the MUMPS library. [13]

LAMMPS

Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS) is a software used for classical molecular dynamics with a focus on material modeling. LAMMPS was used to perform the molecular dynamics simulations needed for the Capriccio method. [5]

MUMPS

MUltifrontal Massively Parallel sparse direct Solver (MUMPS) is a library for the solution of sparse linear systems on multicore computers. It implements methods based on the LDL or LU factorization of the input matrix and is suited for solving square symmetric or asymmetric linear systems. [14] [15]

MATLAB

MATLAB is a programming and numeric computing platform commonly used in engineering. It offers a programming language that expresses matrix and array mathematics directly. Its applications include data analysis, graphics, programming, parallel computing, external language interfaces, and many more.

5 Numerical Examples

Both Capriccio implementations are now used to simulate a sample system in order to evaluate the quality of the point-wise coupling constraint and the performance of the new implementation. To this end, simulations with mostly identical sets of input data and input parameters are performed with both the MATLAB and the Julia version of the Capriccio method.

5.1 Sample System Set-up

The sample system consists of a central silicate glass particle domain which is framed by a continuum discretized into trilinear hexahedral elements. For the particle description of the silicate glass, the material model as described in [16] is used. The general set-up of the sample system is depicted in Figure 5.1. In the continuum, the outer nodes are fixed in such a manner that transverse contractions in y and z directions are not possible. Loads are applied on the system by prescribing the displacements on the outermost nodes of the FE domain in the x direction. For the particle system, a shrink-wrap boundary condition is applied in x direction while the remaining directions have periodic boundaries. The particle domain consists of a Newtonian-dynamics (ND) region represented in blue and a dissipative particle dynamics (DPD) region depicted in red/orange. The particle system and the continuum are coupled by anchor points shown in green.

In total, three simulations were run on the system as described above. Two of those were performed using the original MATLAB implementation; utilizing the integral MLS coupling definition. Here, simulations were run for both the L^2 -norm and the H^1 -norm respectively. The third simulation was performed using the Julia implementation of the Capriccio method written for the purposes of this thesis. Here, the point-wise coupling condition (PWC) as introduced in Section 2.1 was used. Apart from parameters relevant to the coupling schemes, all simulation parameters were kept as identical as possible between all three simulations. A selection of relevant parameters is listed in Table 5.1. It has to be noted that while both implementations use different methods to calculate α , for this specific set-up, the resulting α values are identical between both approaches.

Figure 5.1: Set-up of the coupled MD-FE system: The particle system is framed on opposite sides by finite element domains. The particle domain consists of a Newtonian-dynamics region represented in blue and a dissipative particle dynamics region depicted in red/orange. The particle system and the continuum are coupled by anchor points shown in green.

Table 5.1: Relevant parameters of the coupled simulations of silicate glass used to investigate the quality of the new coupling constraint.

Description	Variable	MATLAB	Julia
Coupling constraint		MLS	point-wise
Norm used for coupling constraint		L^2/H^1 -norm	-
Number of supporting points in MLS aprox.		6	-
Young's modulus in the FE domain	E	$0.454 \text{ eV } \text{\AA}^{-3}$	
Poisson's ratio in the FE domain	ν	0.209	
Strain rate applied in tensile direction	$\dot{\epsilon}_x$	0.25 ns^{-1}	
Continuum model		linear-elastic	
Particle model		SiO_2 (SHIK [16])	
Number of super atoms in the MD domain	n_{MD}	30 035	
Number of anchor points	n_{MS}	6 654	
Number of FE nodes	n_n	336	
Radial force constant anchor points / super atoms	k_I	$1 \text{ eV } \text{\AA}^{-1}$	
Alpha function		linear	
Number of MD-FE iteration steps	\bar{n}	10 000	
Number of MD time steps per MD-FE iteration step	\tilde{n}	50	
Length of an MD time step	Δt	0.0016 ps	
Computation performed at		FAU-HPC	

5.2 Simulation Results

To evaluate the accuracy of the different coupling methods, a closer look is taken at the balance of forces. Since the simulated system is a sandwich system where each domain is connected in series with respect to the direction of the applied load, the section forces in the direction of the applied load should match throughout the entire simulation. Furthermore, because the boundary conditions for the sandwich system are chosen such that there are no transverse contractions, the cross-sectional area remains constant throughout the entire simulation. Therefore, not only the section forces but also the stresses in the direction of the applied load should match.

The stresses at the boundaries of the continuum domain are calculated as the sum of the nodal forces at each Dirichlet boundary divided by the area of the respective boundary. The resulting stresses are then averaged between the two boundaries:

$$\sigma_x = \frac{1}{2A} \left[\sum_{I \in \Gamma_l} \mathbf{F}_I \cdot \mathbf{n}_l + \sum_{I \in \Gamma_r} \mathbf{F}_I \cdot \mathbf{n}_r \right] \quad (5.1)$$

Here, A is the cross-sectional area of the sample in x direction. $I \in \Gamma_r$ denotes the nodes that are part of the right boundary with $I \in \Gamma_l$ denoting the nodes that are part of the left boundary. Furthermore, \mathbf{n}_r and \mathbf{n}_l represent the normal vectors of their respective boundary domain. The stresses in the particle domain are calculated through the sum of the virial tensors of each super atom within a predefined observation region, which is then divided by the volume of said region [3]:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = -\frac{1}{V} \sum_{I \in \Omega} \left[m_I \mathbf{v}_I \otimes \mathbf{v}_I + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{J \in \Omega} (\mathbf{R}_I^{MD} - \mathbf{R}_J^{MD}) \otimes \mathbf{F}_{IJ} \right] \quad (5.2)$$

Here, V is the volume of the observation region and Ω is the set of atoms inside the observation region. \mathbf{F}_{IJ} describes the interaction force applied on atom I by atom J . The resulting stresses arising in each simulation are depicted in Figure 5.2.

Figure 5.2: Stress comparisons for a coupled FE-MD system with different coupling constraints using a linear-elastic material model.

The MLS-coupling definition of the original Capriccio method shows a noticeable mismatch between the finite element simulation and the molecular dynamics region for both the L^2 and the H^1 norm. In contrast, the new pointwise coupling constraint displays

an almost perfect match with respect to the stresses in both regions. This is a strong indicator that the pointwise coupling definition is significantly more reliable at ensuring the balance of forces between the continuum and particle domain.

Notably, the critical applied strain at which the molecular dynamics simulation fractures differs slightly between each coupling method. In general, the MLS simulations appear to have a higher stiffness compared to the point-wise coupling, and looking at the stresses in the MD-domain at which the fracture occurs reveals that the different fracture timings are caused by the different stress responses of the coupled systems, as the sample breaks at roughly the same stress within the observation region of the particle domain, regardless of the chosen coupling method.

Assuming that the pure MD and pure FE domain display the same stress-strain responses regardless of the coupling definition, it is evident that this is due to different stiffnesses resulting in the bridging domain. Specifically, the PWC appears to result in a higher stiffness in the bridging domain compared to the MLS implementations. This is likely due to the fact that the MLS coupling constraint has significantly fewer Lagrange multipliers than there are degrees of freedom for the anchor points. Combined with the fact that the approach of creating a virtual displacement field for the MLS coupling inevitably introduces inaccuracies, the anchor points are not tightly constrained to their initial position in their respective FE element. This allows the anchor points to move slightly relative to the continuum description without transmitting forces, which in turn reduces the stiffness of the bridging domain. A future mathematical investigation of the MLS coupling constraint may reveal further insights as to why the balance of forces is not upheld here. This is, however, outside the scope of this thesis.

Figure 5.3 depicts the state of the coupled system in the Julia implementation at selected stages of applied load. At 0.15 applied strain, while the crack is forming, a bulge in the finite element description on the left-hand side in the vicinity of the crack is clearly visible. This is exactly what is expected to happen, as the stress concentrates in the vicinity of the crack fronts, leaving a zone of low stress on either side of the fracture. Furthermore, on the right-hand side further away from the crack no such bulge is visible, indicating a more uniform stress distribution.

Figure 5.3: State of the coupled system in the Julia implementation at different stages of applied load.

5.3 Performance

The runtime of both implementations was timed to compare their performance. For this, the same sample system presented in Section 5.1 was used, with the MATLAB implementation being run using the L^2 -norm. A timing breakdown is shown in Figure 5.4, with more detailed performance metrics listed in Tables 5.2 and 5.3.

Notably, the Julia implementation runs about six times faster than the MATLAB version for the investigated sample system, with every section of the simulation also showing significant performance increases.

Run MD

A significant amount of the performance improvement of the Julia version stems from the molecular dynamics part of the simulation. However, because both implementations rely on LAMMPS, while using almost identical simulation scripts, a majority of this speedup is likely not to be attributed to faster time stepping. Instead, much of the performance gain is due to the reduced overhead in the Julia implementation, as LAMMPS is not restarted at the beginning of each molecular dynamics iteration. This eliminates the LAMMPS start-up and set-up time from the core simulation loop.

Figure 5.4: Runtime comparison between the MATLAB and Julia implementation of the Capriccio method. The time of a full iteration is highlighted by a gray box. The other measurements pertain a selection of individual runs of an iteration.

Solve FE

The solving of the finite element problem shows a significant speed-up in performance as well. However, there is likely still much performance to be gained here, especially for large finite element systems with a significantly higher amount of degrees of freedom, as most of the matrix and vector operations (addition, multiplication) as well as most other parts of the FE procedure are not properly parallelized yet. A notable exception to this is the solving of the linear equation (2.34), as this is handled by MUMPS. This step is therefore able to take advantage of the parallel capabilities of the HPC system.

Write Solution

The solution of the finite element part of the iteration is written to `.mat` files in MATLAB and to ParaView `.vtu` files in Julia. The Julia implementation only saves selected properties of the solved system. In contrast, the MATLAB version stores the full state of the finite element simulation, as stored in the "FE" struct. The difference in writing performance is likely attributed to the different volume of data which has to be written. In reality, the Julia implementation even performs light post-processing during the write solution phase. Here, the nodal forces are computed, as they are not stored during time-stepping, and stress recovery is performed.

Gather Anchor Forces and Set Displacement

The communication between LAMMPS and the finite element part of the simulation is handled differently in both implementations as discussed in Section 3.2. Therefore, these parts of the timing breakdown entail the reading and writing of dump files for the MATLAB implementation. Notably, they only include the read and write operations

performed by MATLAB, as it is difficult to time these operations within LAMMPS. Instead, they are included in the "run md" section of the timing breakdown. For Julia, the gather anchor forces and set displacements section entail both the projection of per anchor data to nodal values and vice versa as well as the gather and scatter operations used to read/write the updated values directly from/into LAMMPS memory.

Table 5.2: Detailed performance metrics of the Julia implementation.

Section	ncalls	time	%tot	avg time
FEMD-iteration	10.0k	1.37h	100.0%	494ms
Run MD	10.0k	1.27h	92.2%	456ms
Solve FE	10.0k	341s	6.9%	34.1ms
Write solution	2.0k	26.2s	0.5%	13.1ms
Gather anchor forces	10.0k	11.4s	0.2%	1.14ms
Set displacements	10.0k	4.74s	0.1%	474 μ s

Table 5.3: Detailed performance metrics of the MATLAB implementation.

Section	ncalls	time	%tot	avg time
FEMD-iteration	10.0k	8.35h	100%	3.01s
Run MD	10.0k	6.50h	77.8%	2.34s
Solve FE	10.0k	1331s	4.4%	133ms
Write solution	2.0k	381s	1.27%	190ms
Gather anchor forces	10.0k	144s	0.5%	14ms
Set displacements	10.0k	138s	0.5%	14ms

6 Conclusions and Outlook

The newly written implementation of the Capriccio method in Julia shows a significant speedup compared to the previous MATLAB implementation. Due to the direct usage of MPI, this lays the groundwork for a highly efficient, parallel implementation of the Capriccio method in all its details.

The point-wise coupling constraint introduced in this thesis is mathematically simpler while significantly reducing the number of degrees of freedom in the full system of equations of the Capriccio method. A basic numerical example also shows that this coupling definition is more reliable at ensuring a balance of forces than the previous approach, which utilizes a moving least square approximation. It appears plausible that the point-wise coupling constraint can serve as a basis for a Capriccio method which does not rely on a staggered solution scheme but instead solves both the equations of the finite element and the particle domains in synchronization with each other by applying the same explicit time-stepping scheme to both problems.

A new approach to calculating the alpha value needed for the energy blending in the Capriccio method with the aim of providing a definition of alpha that is well-defined in two or three dimensions is also introduced. As it uses the same discretization as the finite element description of the continuum and bridging domain, it is easy to implement within the context of the Capriccio method. However, it can be shown that the local coordinate field ξ is not always linear compared to appropriate coordinate systems that can describe the bridging domain using a single coordinate. While this likely has little impact on the results of the simulation, other definitions that improve on this linearity problem may be investigated.

The energy blending inside the bridging domain is currently only implemented for the continuum contribution to the total energy. A proper implementation of the energy blending of the particle contribution still has to be investigated and implemented.

Additionally, Capriccio Julia currently only has implementations for the linear-elastic and Neo-Hooke material models. Other material models that are better at describing the deformation behavior of polymers may be implemented in future improvements to the software.

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A Installation and Usage

In the following appendix the installation of the Julia implementation of the Capriccio method as well as its dependencies is outlined. It is assumed here, that the implementation is to be installed on the Fritz computing cluster. After establishing a connection to one of the login nodes of the Fritz computing cluster via ssh it is first necessary to load an MPI module. This module needs to be loaded during the entire installation process and whenever running the CapriccioSimulation project. Here OpenMPI is used, however, other MPI implementations should work as well.

```
$ module load openmpi/4.1.3-nvhpc22.3
```

If this does not work, try opening a login shell in your ssh session

```
$ bash -l
```

Installing Julia

Julia can be installed with

```
$ curl -fsSL https://install.julialang.org | sh
```

You may need to manually add `./juliaup/bin/` to your PATH variable by adding

```
export PATH="$PATH:~/.juliaup/bin"
```

to your `.bashrc` file. Additionally, you should add

```
if [ -f ~/.bashrc ]; then
    source ~/.bashrc
fi
```

to your `.bash_profile` file in order to have access to Julia in a login shell. Then, run

```
$ source ~/.bashrc
```

Julia should now be accessible with the `julia` command.

Installing LAMMPS

The LAMMPS installation used for this thesis is installed with:

```
$ git clone -b stable https://github.com/lammps/lammps.git

# external pair files not included with LAMMPS
$ git clone https://github.com/compmatsscirpi/SHIK-potential
$ cp SHIK-potential/pair_SHIK_wolf.* lammps/src

$ cd lammps/src

$ make yes-MOLECULE
$ make yes-MPIIO
$ make yes-KSPACE
$ make yes-INTEL
$ make yes-NETCDF
$ make yes-MISC
$ make yes-CLASS2
$ make yes-MOLFILE
$ make yes-OPT
$ make yes-MANYBODY
$ make yes-DPD-BASIC
$ make yes-EXTRA-DUMP
$ make yes-MC
$ make yes-EXTRA-FIX
$ make yes-EXTRA-MOLECULE
$ make yes-EXTRA-PAIR
$ make yes-REACTION
$ make yes-bpm

$ make mode=shared mpi
```

it is important that LAMMPS is compiled as a shared library (.so/.dll file ending) for Julia to be able to interface with it. Furthermore, if you do not need a custom LAMMPS installation for your simulation, you may be able to skip this step, as LAMMPS.jl comes with a precompiled binary which already has most packages enabled.

Installing MUMPS

A precompiled binary is shipped with the Julia wrapper library MUMPS.jl. For Windows machines you have to provide your own installation, as MUMPS.jl doesn't have a precompiled binary for this platform.

Installing Capriccio-Julia

To install Capriccio-Julia, first, you need to download Capriccio-Julia into your home directory. Next, the CapriccioSimulation project has to be configured to use the MPI binary of the HPC cluster and your custom LAMMPS installation:¹

¹The `-project` command line flag instructs Julia to load the project specified in the `Project.toml` and `Manifest.toml` files in the current directory. The `Project.toml` file declares the dependencies needed for

```
$ cd ~/capriccio-julia/CapriccioSimulation
$ julia --project
julia> using MPIPreferences, LAMMPS
julia> use_system_binary()
julia> LAMMPS.set_library!("~/lammps/src/liblammps_mpi.so")
```

These configurations are stored in the LocalPreferences.toml file. If you want to use the LAMMPS binary included with LAMMPS.jl, you should skip the last command. Additionally, you may want to run

```
julia> ] precompile
```

to ensure that all dependencies are downloaded and precompiled.² To exit Julia, simply use the `exit()` function.

Running the Simulation

The simulation files are set up to run on the Fritz cluster using the slurm workload manager. To start the simulation, you need to be in the CapriccioSimulation folder (where the Project.toml file is located). Then, simply run the batch script:

```
$ cd ~/capriccio-julia/CapriccioSimulation
$ sbatch scripts/Silica/Silica.sh
```

The simulation uses `$FASTTMP/Silica_${SLURM_JOB_ID}` as the working directory. After completing the simulation, this directory gets stored as a .zip archive in the vault file system (`$HPCVAULT/Silica_${SLURM_JOB_ID}.zip`).

For testing purposes, you may want to limit the requested computation time to 20 minutes in order to receive higher priority for scheduling, as tasks shorter than 1 hour often start immediately.

Evaluating Results

The CapriccioAnalysis folder contains a loose collection of small scripts that were used to evaluate the results and create various figures. They are intended to run on your local machine and do not need the MPI module loaded or any custom set-up for LAMMPS or MPI. You may need to modify these scripts slightly (especially file paths) in order for them to work correctly. You should see them rather as a starting of point for your own analysis of your results than as fully worked out programs.

the project while the Manifest.toml file keeps track of the specific versions of the dependencies and any sub-dependencies (so dependencies of dependencies).

²Typing `]` as the first character in the julia REPL (read evaluate print loop) opens the Julia package manager. Similarly, typing `'?` switches Julia into help mode and `;` activates the command line mode. To return to Julia, simply press the backspace key (at the start of the command). Type `] help` in the REPL to learn more about the package manager.

B Source Code

Directory tree

```
CapriccioSimulation
├── scripts
│   └── Silica
│       ├── Silica.sh
│       └── input
│           ├── potentials.lmpmod
│           ├── silica.data
│           ├── silica.inp
│           ├── Silica.jl
│           └── silica.lmp
├── src
│   ├── CapriccioSimulation.jl
│   ├── AlphaHandler.jl
│   ├── FerriteWrappers.jl
│   ├── fe_code.jl
│   ├── md_code.jl
│   └── FiniteElementModels
│       ├── Linearelasticity.jl
│       └── Hyperelasticity.jl
└── Project.toml
```

Code

Listing B.1: Silica.sh.

```
1 #!/bin/bash -l
2 #
3 #SBATCH --partition=singlenode
4 #SBATCH --nodes=1
5 #SBATCH --ntasks-per-node=72
6 #SBATCH --cpus-per-task=1
7 #SBATCH --time=02:00:00
8 #SBATCH --export=NONE
9 #SBATCH --output=/dev/null
10 #SBATCH --error=/dev/null
11
12 WORKDIR=$FASTTMP/Silica_${SLURM_JOB_ID}
13 mkdir $WORKDIR
14 mkdir $WORKDIR/output
15 exec > $WORKDIR/output/log.txt 2>&1
16 cp -r scripts/Silica/. $WORKDIR
17 cd $WORKDIR
18
19 unset SLURM_EXPORT_ENV
20 module load openmpi/4.1.3-nvhpc22.3
21
22 srun julia --project=$SLURM_SUBMIT_DIR -- input/Silica.jl
```

```
23
24 zip -r $HPCVAULT/Silica_$SLURM_JOB_ID.zip .
```

Listing B.2: Silica.jl.

```
1 using CapriccioSimulation
2 using Ferrite
3 using WriteVTK
4 using LAMMPS
5 using MPI
6 using TimerOutputs
7
8 #####
9 # Preparation #
10 #####
11
12 MPI.Init()
13 rank = MPI.Comm_rank(MPI.COMM_WORLD)
14
15 #####
16 # Parameters #
17 #####
18
19 tol = 1e-07
20 maxiter = 10
21 md_steps = 50
22 anchor_stiffness = 1
23 material = Hooke(0.454340774282867, 0.209256875807888)
24 fe_output_freq = 5
25
26 load_steps = range(start=0, stop=0.2, length=10000)
27
28 lammmps_prm = Dict(
29     "anchor_stiffness" => anchor_stiffness/2,
30     "timestep" => 0.0016,
31     "boundary_beads" => 0,
32     "boundary_x" => 's',
33     "boundary_y" => 'p',
34     "boundary_z" => 'p',
35     "constraint_x" => 0,
36     "constraint_y" => 1,
37     "constraint_z" => 1,
38     "Tstart" => 300,
39     "Tend" => 300,
40     "dpd_friction_coeff" => 0.1,
41     "initial_energy_minimization" => "no",
42     "initial_velocities" => "yes",
43     "wall_reflect" => "yes",
44     "anchorforce_avg_every" => 1,
45     "anchorforce_avg_repeat" => md_steps,
46     "anchorforce_output" => md_steps,
47     "obsregion_x" => 60,
48     "obsregion_y" => 60,
49     "obsregion_z" => 45,
50     "output" => 10,
51     "trj_out" => 2500
52 )
53
54 #####
55 # FE Definition #
56 #####
57
58 grid = load_grid("input/silica.inp")
59 dof = vector_dof_handler(grid, :u, ["FE1", "FE2", "BD1", "BD2"])
60
61 ch = ConstraintHandler(dof)
62
```

```

63 Boun1 = getnodeset(grid, "BOUN_1")
64 add!(ch, Dirichlet(:u, Boun1, x-> 0, 2))
65
66 Boun2 = getnodeset(grid, "BOUN_2")
67 add!(ch, Dirichlet(:u, Boun2, x-> 0, 3))
68
69 Dspl1 = getnodeset(grid, "DSPL_1")
70 add!(ch, Dirichlet(:u, Dspl1, (x,t)-> 60t, 1))
71
72 Dspl2 = getnodeset(grid, "DSPL_2")
73 add!(ch, Dirichlet(:u, Dspl2, (x,t)-> -60t, 1))
74
75 close!(ch)
76
77  $\alpha_{\text{fun}}(\xi) = \xi$ 
78
79 alpha = AlphaHandler(grid, [
80     "FE1" => 1.0,
81     "FE2" => 1.0,
82     "MD"  => 0.0,
83     "BD1" => NaN,
84     "BD2" => NaN
85 ],  $\alpha_{\text{fun}}$ )
86
87 proj = projector(dof)
88
89 #####
90 # MD Definition #
91 #####
92
93 lmp = LMP(["-sf", "opt", "-log", "output/log.lammps"])
94 set_variables!(lmp, lammps_prm)
95 command(lmp, "include input/silica.lmp")
96 anchor = AnchorAtoms(lmp, "anchor", dof, anchor_stiffness)
97
98 #####
99 # Run Simulation #
100 #####
101
102 K_ext = get_embedded_stiffness(anchor)
103
104 if iszero(rank)
105     pvd = paraview_collection("output/fe-md-simulation")
106 end
107
108 assembler = create_assembler(material, dof, alpha)
109 u = system_vector(dof)
110
111 for (step, strain) in enumerate(load_steps)
112     @timeit "FEMD-Iteratrion" begin
113         @timeit "set displacements" set_displacements!(anchor, u)
114         @timeit "run md" run_md!(lmp, md_steps)
115         @timeit "gather anchorforces" f_ext = get_anchorforces(anchor, "
            f_anchorforce_avg")
116         @timeit "update constraints" update!(ch, strain)
117         @timeit "solve fe" global u = solve_fe!(u, assembler, ch, K_ext, f_ext;
            tol, maxiter)
118
119         if iszero(rank) && iszero((step-1) % fe_output_freq)
120             @timeit "write solution" VTKGridFile("output/fe-md-simulation- $\$$ step"
                , dof) do vtk
121                 write_solution(vtk, dof, u)
122                 f = compute_forces(assembler, u) + K_ext * u - f_ext
123                 write_solution(vtk, dof, f, "forces")
124                 Ferrite.write_nodeset(vtk, grid, "DSPL_1")
125                 Ferrite.write_nodeset(vtk, grid, "DSPL_2")
126                  $\sigma$  = compute_stresses(assembler, u)
127                  $\sigma_{\text{nodes}}$  = project(proj,  $\sigma$ )
128                 write_projection(vtk, proj,  $\sigma_{\text{nodes}}$ , "stress")
129

```

```

130         pvd[get_ntimestep(lmp)] = vtk
131     end
132 end
133 end
134
135 if iszero(rank)
136     print_timer(linechars = :ascii)
137 end
138 end
139
140 if iszero(rank)
141     vtk_save(pvd)
142 end
143
144 MPI.Finalize()

```

Listing B.3: Silica.lmp.

```

1 # neighbor list: extra distance beyond force cutoff
2 variable skin equal "v_neighListCutoff-v_nbCutoff" # internal
3
4 # Simulation parameters
5 units metal # set of units used throughout the MD simulation
6 processors * * * # number of processors chosen by lammmps
7 atom_style full # format of data file
8 boundary ${boundary_x} ${boundary_y} ${boundary_z} # style of
    box boundaries in each dimension
9
10 read_data input/silica.data
11
12 include input/potentials.lmpmod
13
14 # Communicate velocities b/w CPUs. Needed for the hybrid style.
15 #comm_style tiled
16 comm_modify vel yes
17
18 # Timestep setting
19 timestep ${timestep}
20
21 # Groups
22 group md type 1 2
23 group anchor type 3
24 group dpd type 4 5
25 group fur type 6 7
26 group mob type 1 2 4 5
27
28
29 #obs group
30 variable obscorner_x equal ${obsregion_x}/2
31 variable obscorner_y equal ${obsregion_y}/2
32 variable obscorner_z equal ${obsregion_z}/2
33 region obsreg block -${obscorner_x} ${obscorner_x} -${obscorner_y} ${obscorner_y}
    -${obscorner_z} ${obscorner_z}
34 group obs dynamic all region obsreg
35 variable volobs equal ${obsregion_x}*${obsregion_y}*${obsregion_z}
36 # Density compute
37 variable obsdens equal (mass(obs)/${volobs}) # Units?
38
39 # Atom counter
40 variable mdcount equal count(md)
41 variable dpdcount equal count(dpd)
42 variable furcount equal count(fur)
43 variable obscount equal count(obs)
44
45 # Temp computes
46 compute mdtemp md temp
47 compute dpdtemp dpd temp

```

```

48
49 # Anchor point force averaging and output
50 fix anchorforce_avg anchor ave/atom ${anchorforce_avg_every} ${
    anchorforce_avg_repeat} ${anchorforce_output} fx fy fz
51
52 # Start dumping data
53 dump          trajectory all custom ${trj_out} output/silica.lammpstrj id x y z
    # vx vy vz ix iy iz
54
55 # Observed region stress calculation
56 compute       peratom obs stress/atom NULL
57 compute       pobs obs reduce sum c_peratom[1] c_peratom[2] c_peratom[3]
    c_peratom[4] c_peratom[5] c_peratom[6]
58 variable     obsstressxx equal "(c_pobs[1]/v_volobs)"
59 variable     obsstressyy equal "(c_pobs[2]/v_volobs)"
60 variable     obsstresszz equal "(c_pobs[3]/v_volobs)"
61 variable     obsstressxy equal "(c_pobs[4]/v_volobs)"
62 variable     obsstressxz equal "(c_pobs[5]/v_volobs)"
63 variable     obsstressyz equal "(c_pobs[6]/v_volobs)"
64
65
66
67 # On-the-fly calculations of thermodynamics
68 thermo       ${output}
69 thermo_style  custom step etotal pe ke epair ebond evdwl ecoutl elong temp press
    pxx pyy pzz pxy pxz pyz lx ly lz density v_obsdens c_mdtemp c_dpdttemp
    v_obsstressxx v_obsstressyy v_obsstresszz v_obsstressxy v_obsstressxz
    v_obsstressyz v_mdcount v_dpdcount v_furcount v_obscount # thermo output
70 thermo_modify lost warn flush yes
71
72
73 # Energy minimization
74 if "${initial_energy_minimization} == yes" then &
75     "min_style      cg" &
76     "min_modify     dmax 0.01" &
77     "minimize       0 1.0e-4 1000000 10000000"
78
79
80 if "${boundary_x}==p && ${constraint_x}==0 && ${boundary_y}==p && ${constraint_y}
    ==0 && ${boundary_z}==p && ${constraint_z}==0" then &
81     "fix          lateral mob press/berendsen x 0.0 0.0 $(1000.0*dt) y 0.0 0.0
    $(1000.0*dt) z 0.0 0.0 $(1000.0*dt) dilate partial" &
82 elif "${boundary_y}==p && ${constraint_y}==0 && ${boundary_z}==p && ${
    constraint_z}==0" &
83     "fix          lateral mob press/berendsen y 0.0 0.0 $(1000.0*dt) z 0.0 0.0
    $(1000.0*dt) dilate partial" &
84 elif "${boundary_z}==p && ${constraint_z}==0" &
85     "fix          lateral mob press/berendsen z 0.0 0.0 $(1000.0*dt) dilate
    partial"
86
87 if "${initial_velocities} == yes" then &
88     "velocity mob create ${Tstart} 5287287"
89
90 if "${wall_reflect} == yes && ${boundary_x}==s && ${boundary_y}==s && ${
    boundary_z}==s" then &
91     "fix walls all wall/reflect xlo EDGE xhi EDGE ylo EDGE yhi EDGE zlo EDGE
    zhi EDGE" &
92 elif "${wall_reflect} == yes && ${boundary_x}==s && ${boundary_y}==s" &
93     "fix walls all wall/reflect xlo EDGE xhi EDGE ylo EDGE yhi EDGE"
94
95 # RUN with time integrator
96 fix runfix mob nve

```

Listing B.4: potentials.lmpmod.

```

1 variable Si equal 1
2 variable O equal 2

```

```

3 variable Sidpd equal 4
4 variable Odpd equal 5
5 variable Sifur equal 6
6 variable Ofur equal 7
7
8 #Modify dump command to output the correct atomic species
9 variable DUMP_STRING string "Si O"
10
11 #-----ATOM DEFINITION-----#
12
13 ### Define atom groups
14 group Si type ${Si}
15 group O type ${O}
16
17 ### Set electric charge and mass
18 set group Si charge +1.7755
19 mass ${Si} 28.086
20 set group O charge -0.88775
21 mass ${O} 16.0
22
23 #-----INTERATOMIC POTENTIAL AND OUTPUT-----#
24 pair_style hybrid/overlay shik/wolf 8.0 10.0 dpd/tstat ${Tstart} ${Tend} 10.0
    12345
25
26 variable A_ij_Si_Si equal 2798.0
27 variable rho_ij_Si_Si equal 4.4073
28 variable C_ij_Si_Si equal 0.0
29 variable D_ij_Si_Si equal 3423204
30
31 variable A_ij_Si_O equal 23108
32 variable rho_ij_Si_O equal 5.0979
33 variable C_ij_Si_O equal 139.70
34 variable D_ij_Si_O equal 66
35
36 variable A_ij_O_O equal 1120.5
37 variable rho_ij_O_O equal 2.8927
38 variable C_ij_O_O equal 26.132
39 variable D_ij_O_O equal 16800
40
41 variable cutoff1 equal 0.2
42 variable cutoff2 equal 0.2
43
44 pair_coeff * * shik/wolf 0.0 0.1 0.0 0.0 ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}
45 pair_coeff ${Si} ${Si} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_Si} ${rho_ij_Si_Si} ${C_ij_Si_Si} ${
    D_ij_Si_Si} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}
46 pair_coeff ${Si} ${O} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_O} ${rho_ij_Si_O} ${C_ij_Si_O} ${
    D_ij_Si_O} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}
47 pair_coeff ${O} ${O} shik/wolf ${A_ij_O_O} ${rho_ij_O_O} ${C_ij_O_O} ${D_ij_O_O}
    ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}
48 pair_coeff ${Si} ${Sidpd} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_Si} ${rho_ij_Si_Si} ${C_ij_Si_Si}
    ${D_ij_Si_Si} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}
49 pair_coeff ${Si} ${Odpd} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_O} ${rho_ij_Si_O} ${C_ij_Si_O} ${
    D_ij_Si_O} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}
50 pair_coeff ${O} ${Sidpd} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_O} ${rho_ij_Si_O} ${C_ij_Si_O} ${
    D_ij_Si_O} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}
51 pair_coeff ${O} ${Odpd} shik/wolf ${A_ij_O_O} ${rho_ij_O_O} ${C_ij_O_O} ${
    D_ij_O_O} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}
52 pair_coeff ${Sidpd} ${Sidpd} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_Si} ${rho_ij_Si_Si} ${
    C_ij_Si_Si} ${D_ij_Si_Si} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}
53 pair_coeff ${Sidpd} ${Odpd} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_O} ${rho_ij_Si_O} ${C_ij_Si_O} ${
    D_ij_Si_O} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}
54 pair_coeff ${Odpd} ${Odpd} shik/wolf ${A_ij_O_O} ${rho_ij_O_O} ${C_ij_O_O} ${
    D_ij_O_O} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}
55
56 if "(${boundary_beads}==1 || ${boundary_beads}==2)" then&
57     "pair_coeff ${Si} ${Sifur} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_Si} ${rho_ij_Si_Si} ${
        C_ij_Si_Si} ${D_ij_Si_Si} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}" &
58     "pair_coeff ${Si} ${Ofur} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_O} ${rho_ij_Si_O} ${C_ij_Si_O}
        ${D_ij_Si_O} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}" &

```

```

59 "pair_coeff ${O} ${Ofur} shik/wolf ${A_ij_O_O} ${rho_ij_O_O} ${C_ij_O_O} ${
    D_ij_O_O} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}" &
60 "pair_coeff ${Sidpd} ${Sifur} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_Si} ${rho_ij_Si_Si} ${
    C_ij_Si_Si} ${D_ij_Si_Si} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}" &
61 "pair_coeff ${Sidpd} ${Ofur} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_O} ${rho_ij_Si_O} ${
    C_ij_Si_O} ${D_ij_Si_O} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}" &
62 "pair_coeff ${Odpd} ${Ofur} shik/wolf ${A_ij_O_O} ${rho_ij_O_O} ${C_ij_O_O}
    ${D_ij_O_O} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}" &
63 "pair_coeff ${Si} ${Sifur} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_Si} ${rho_ij_Si_Si} ${
    C_ij_Si_Si} ${D_ij_Si_Si} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}" &
64 "pair_coeff ${O} ${Sifur} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_O} ${rho_ij_Si_O} ${C_ij_Si_O}
    ${D_ij_Si_O} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}" &
65 "pair_coeff ${Sidpd} ${Sifur} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_Si} ${rho_ij_Si_Si} ${
    C_ij_Si_Si} ${D_ij_Si_Si} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}" &
66 "pair_coeff ${Odpd} ${Sifur} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_O} ${rho_ij_Si_O} ${
    C_ij_Si_O} ${D_ij_Si_O} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}" &
67 "pair_coeff ${Sifur} ${Sifur} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_Si} ${rho_ij_Si_Si} ${
    C_ij_Si_Si} ${D_ij_Si_Si} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}" &
68 "pair_coeff ${Sifur} ${Ofur} shik/wolf ${A_ij_Si_O} ${rho_ij_Si_O} ${
    C_ij_Si_O} ${D_ij_Si_O} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}" &
69 "pair_coeff ${Ofur} ${Ofur} shik/wolf ${A_ij_O_O} ${rho_ij_O_O} ${C_ij_O_O}
    ${D_ij_O_O} ${cutoff1} ${cutoff2}"
70
71 pair_coeff ${Sidpd} ${Sidpd} dpd/tstat ${dpd_friction_coeff}
72 pair_coeff ${Sidpd} ${Odpd} dpd/tstat ${dpd_friction_coeff}
73 pair_coeff ${Odpd} ${Odpd} dpd/tstat ${dpd_friction_coeff}
74
75 neighbor 0.3 bin
76 neigh_modify every 1 delay 0 check no exclude type 1 3 exclude type 2 3 exclude
    type 3 3 exclude type 3 4 exclude type 3 5
77
78 bond_style harmonic
79 bond_coeff 1 ${anchor_stiffness} 0.0

```

Listing B.5: Project.toml.

```

1 name = "CapriccioSimulation"
2 uuid = "da02658e-a6a1-4bef-9d5a-ba5b7e90ce37"
3 version = "0.1.0"
4
5 [deps]
6 Ferrite = "c061ca5d-56c9-439f-9c0e-210fe06d3992"
7 FerriteMeshParser = "0f8c756f-80dd-4a75-85c6-b0a5ab9d4620"
8 LAMMPS = "ee2e13b9-eee9-4449-aafa-cfa6a2dbe14d"
9 LinearAlgebra = "37e2e46d-f89d-539d-b4ee-838fcccc9c8e"
10 MPI = "da04e1cc-30fd-572f-bb4f-1f8673147195"
11 MPIPreferences = "3da0fdf6-3ccc-4f1b-acd9-58baa6c99267"
12 MUMPS = "55d2b088-9f4e-11e9-26c0-150b02ea6a46"
13 OpenMPI_jll = "fe0851c0-eeed-5654-98d4-656369965a5c"
14 SparseArrays = "2f01184e-e22b-5df5-ae63-d93ebab69eaf"
15 TimerOutputs = "a759f4b9-e2f1-59dc-863e-4aeb61b1ea8f"
16 WriteVTK = "64499a7a-5c06-52f2-abe2-ccb03c286192"
17
18 [compat]
19 Ferrite = "=1.0.0"
20 FerriteMeshParser = "=0.2.0"
21 LAMMPS = "=0.7.2"
22 MPI = "=0.20.22"
23 MPIPreferences = "=0.1.11"
24 MUMPS = "=1.4.1"
25 OpenMPI_jll = "=4.1.6"
26 SparseArrays = "=1.10.0"
27 TimerOutputs = "=0.5.24"
28 WriteVTK = "=1.20"
29
30 [extras]
31 LAMMPS_jll = "5b3ab26d-9607-527c-88ea-8fe5ba57cafe"

```

Listing B.6: CapriccioSimulation.jl.

```
1 module CapriccioSimulation
2
3 using Ferrite
4 using FerriteMeshParser
5 using LAMMPS
6 using MUMPS
7 using MPI
8 using SparseArrays
9 using LinearAlgebra
10 using TimerOutputs
11
12 export
13     # FerriteWrappers
14     load_grid,
15     vector_dof_handler,
16     system_vector,
17     get_cells,
18     projector,
19
20     # Element Models
21     create_assembler,
22     stiffness_matrix,
23     compute_stresses,
24     compute_forces,
25     Hooke,
26     NeoHooke,
27
28     # md code
29     FurAtoms,
30     AnchorAtoms,
31     get_embedded_stiffness,
32     set_displacements!,
33     get_anchorforces,
34     get_ntimestep,
35     set_variables!,
36     run_md!,
37
38     # fe code
39     solve_fe!,
40
41     # AlphaHandler
42     AlphaHandler
43
44 include("md_code.jl")
45 include("fe_code.jl")
46 include("AlphaHandler.jl")
47 include("FerriteWrappers.jl")
48
49 include("FiniteElementModels/Linearelasticity.jl")
50 include("FiniteElementModels/Hyperelasticity.jl")
51
52 end # module CapriccioFEMD
```

Listing B.7: AlphaHandler.jl.

```
1 #####
2 # AlphaHandler #
3 #####
4
5 struct AlphaHandler{DH<:DofHandler, F<:Function}
```

```

6     dh::DH
7     ξ::Vector{Float64}
8     α_fun::F
9  end
10
11  function AlphaHandler(grid::Grid, domains, α_fun=identity)
12     domains_dict = Dict(domains)
13
14     dh = scalar_dof_handler(grid, :ξ, keys(domains_dict))
15     ch = ConstraintHandler(dh)
16
17     for (setname, value) in domains
18         isnan(value) && continue
19         add!(ch, Dirichlet(:ξ, getnodeset(grid, setname), Returns(value)))
20     end
21
22     close!(ch)
23
24     free = ch.free_dofs
25     prescribed = ch.prescribed_dofs
26
27     ξ = system_vector(dh)
28     ξ[prescribed] = ch.inhomogeneities
29
30     if length(free) > 0
31         Ke = element_matrix(dh)
32         K = allocate_matrix(dh)
33         assembler = start_assemble(K)
34         cellvalues = cell_values(dh)
35
36         cellset = collect(only(dh.subdofhandlers).cellset)
37         owned_elements = cellset[MPI.Comm_rank(MPI.COMM_WORLD)+1:MPI.Comm_size(
38             MPI.COMM_WORLD):end]
39
40         for cell in CellIterator(dh, owned_elements)
41             Ferrite.reinit!(cellvalues, cell)
42             fill!(Ke, 0)
43
44             for qp in 1:getnquadpoints(cellvalues)
45                 dΩ = getdetJdV(cellvalues, qp)
46
47                 for I in CartesianIndices(Ke)
48                     ∇u = shape_gradient(cellvalues, qp, I[1])
49                     ∇u = shape_gradient(cellvalues, qp, I[2])
50                     Ke[I] += (∇u · ∇u) * dΩ
51                 end
52             end
53
54             assemble!(assembler, celldofs(cell), Ke)
55         end
56
57         MPI.Allreduce!(K.nzval, +, MPI.COMM_WORLD)
58         ξ[free] = - vec(solve(K[free, free], (K[free, prescribed] * ξ[prescribed]
59             )))
60     end
61
62     MPI.Bcast!(ξ, MPI.COMM_WORLD)
63     return AlphaHandler(dh, ξ, α_fun)
64 end
65
66 #####
67 # AlphaValues #
68 #####
69
70 struct AlphaValues{DH<:DofHandler}
71     av::AlphaHandler{DH}
72     shape_values::Matrix{Float64}
73     dofs::Vector{Int}
74     alpha_values::Vector{Float64}
75 end

```

```

74
75 function AlphaValues(bc::AlphaHandler, order=2)
76     ip = get_ip(bc.dh)
77     refshape = getrefshape(ip)
78     qr = QuadratureRule{refshape}(order)
79
80     n = getnbasefunctions(ip)
81     m = getnquadpoints(qr)
82
83     shape_values = Matrix{Float64}(undef, (n, m))
84     Ferrite.reference_shape_values!(shape_values, ip, qr.points)
85     dofs = zeros{Int, ndofs_per_cell(bc.dh)}
86
87     return AlphaValues(bc, shape_values, dofs, zeros(m))
88 end
89
90 function Ferrite.reinit!(av::AlphaValues, cell::Int)
91     celldofs!(av.dofs, av.av.dh, cell)
92     node_values = @view av.av.ξ[av.dofs]
93
94     if allequal(node_values)
95         # this ensures that the coordinate_values are always exactly
96         # 0.0 or exactly 1.0 when inside a pure domain
97         fill!(av.alpha_values, first(node_values) |> av.av.α_fun)
98     else
99         mul!(av.alpha_values, av.shape_values', node_values)
100        av.alpha_values .= av.av.α_fun.(av.alpha_values)
101    end
102    return av
103 end
104
105 Ferrite.reinit!(av::AlphaValues, cell::CellCache) = Ferrite.reinit!(av, cellid(
    cell))
106
107 function alpha_value(bcd::AlphaValues, q_point::Int)
108     return bcd.alpha_values[q_point]
109 end
110
111 #####
112 # Show #
113 #####
114
115 function Base.show(io::IO, ::MIME"text/plain", bd_alpha::AlphaHandler)
116     println(io, "AlphaHandler with $(length(bd_alpha.ξ)) nodes")
117 end
118
119 function Base.show(io::IO, ::MIME"text/plain", bcd::AlphaValues)
120     println(io, "AlphaValues: $(size(bcd.shape_values, 2)) quadrature points")
121     println(io, "  interpolation: $(get_ip(bcd.av.dh))")
122 end

```

Listing B.8: FerriteWrappers.jl.

```

1 Ferrite.geometric_interpolation(grid::Grid) = geometric_interpolation(
    getcelltype(grid))
2
3 function _dof_handler(grid, name, setnames, ip)
4     dh = DofHandler(grid)
5
6     if isnothing(setnames)
7         add!(dh, name, ip)
8     else
9         cellset = mapreduce(union, setnames) do setname
10            getcellset(grid, setname)
11     end
12
13     sdh = SubDofHandler(dh, cellset)

```

```

14     add!(sdh, name, ip)
15     end
16
17     close!(dh)
18 end
19
20 """
21     scalar_dof_handler(grid::AbstractGrid, name::Symbol, setnames=nothing)
22
23 Convenience method for creating a DofHandler with a single scalar field on a
24 given subdomain.
25
26 # Arguments
27 - `grid::AbstractGrid`: The finite element grid.
28 - `name::Symbol`: The name of the DoF field.
29 - `setnames`: An optional list of cell set names to restrict the DoF handler to
30 specific cell sets.
31
32 # Example
33 ```julia
34 scalar_dof_handler(grid, :ξ, "MD")
35 ```
36 """
37 function scalar_dof_handler(grid::Grid, name::Symbol, setnames=nothing)
38     ip = geometric_interpolation(grid)
39     return _dof_handler(grid, name, setnames, ip)
40 end
41
42 """
43     vector_dof_handler(grid::AbstractGrid, name::Symbol, setnames=nothing)
44
45 Convenience method for creating a DofHandler with a single vector field on a
46 given subdomain.
47
48 # Arguments
49 - `grid::AbstractGrid`: The finite element grid.
50 - `name::Symbol`: The name of the DoF field.
51 - `setnames`: An optional list of cell set names to restrict the DoF handler to
52 specific cell sets.
53
54 # Example
55 ```julia
56 vector_dof_handler(grid, :u, "FE")
57 ```
58 """
59 function vector_dof_handler(grid::Grid, name::Symbol, setnames=nothing)
60     ip = VectorizedInterpolation(geometric_interpolation(grid))
61     return _dof_handler(grid, name, setnames, ip)
62 end
63
64 get_sub(dh::DofHandler) = only(dh.subdofhandlers)
65 get_ip(dh::DofHandler) = only(get_sub(dh).field_interpolations)
66 get_field(dh::DofHandler) = only(get_sub(dh).field_names)
67 get_cells(dh::DofHandler) = get_sub(dh).cellset
68
69 """
70     cell_values(dh::DofHandler, order=2)
71
72 Convenience method for creating a `CellValues` object.
73
74 This method assumes that the DofHandler only has a single SubDofHandler with a
75 single Field.
76
77 """
78 function cell_values(dh::DofHandler, order=2)
79     ip = get_ip(dh)
80     refshape = getrefshape(ip)
81     qr = QuadratureRule{refshape}(order)
82
83     return CellValues(qr, ip)
84 end

```

```

79
80 function element_matrix(dh::DofHandler)
81     n = ndofs_per_cell(dh)
82     return zeros(n, n)
83 end
84
85 element_vector(dh::DofHandler) = zeros(ndofs_per_cell(dh))
86 system_vector(dh::DofHandler) = zeros(ndofs(dh))
87
88 function load_grid(filename::String)
89     grid = get_ferrite_grid(filename)
90     values(grid.nodesets) .|> sort!
91     values(grid.cellsets) .|> sort!
92     return grid
93 end
94
95 function deformation_gradient(cv::CellValues, qp, u, dofs)
96     ∇u = function_gradient(cv, qp, u, dofs)
97     return one(∇u) + ∇u
98 end
99
100 function projector(dof, order=2)
101     ip = get_ip(dof)
102     refshape = getrefshape(ip)
103     qr = QuadratureRule{refshape}(order)
104     set = get_cells(dof)
105
106     proj = L2Projector(dof.grid)
107     add!(proj, set, ip; qr_rhs=qr, qr_lhs=qr)
108     close!(proj)
109 end

```

Listing B.9: fe_code.jl.

```

1 function solve_fe!(u, assembler, ch::ConstraintHandler, K_ext, f_ext; tol=1e-7,
2     maxiter=Inf)
3
4     for iter in Iterators.countfrom()
5         (K, r) = stiffness_matrix(assembler, u)
6         r_ges = r + K_ext*u - f_ext
7         K_ges = K + K_ext
8         apply_zero!(K_ges, r_ges, ch)
9         norm_r = norm(r_ges)
10        norm_r <= tol && break
11        iter >= maxiter && error()
12
13        Δdispl = vec(solve(K_ges, r_ges))
14        MPI.Bcast!(Δdispl, MPI.COMM_WORLD)
15
16        u -= apply_zero!(Δdispl, ch)
17    end
18
19    return u
20 end

```

Listing B.10: md_code.jl.

```

1 #####
2 # Utilities #
3 #####
4
5 function set_variables!(lmp::LMP, vars)
6     for (key, value) in vars

```

```

7     command(lmp, "variable $key string \"\$value\")
8     end
9 end
10
11 run_md!(lmp::LMP, md_steps) = command(lmp, "run $md_steps")
12 get_ntimestep(lmp::LMP) = extract_global(lmp, "ntimestep", LAMMPS_INT64[])
13
14 struct AtomGroup
15     lmp::LMP
16     ids::Vector{Int32}
17
18     function AtomGroup(lmp, group::String="all")
19         ids = group_to_atom_ids(lmp, group)
20         return new(lmp, ids)
21     end
22 end
23
24 LAMMPS.gather(atoms::AtomGroup, name::String, T) = LAMMPS.gather(atoms.lmp, name
, T, atoms.ids)
25 LAMMPS.scatter!(atoms::AtomGroup, name::String, data) = LAMMPS.scatter!(atoms.
lmp, name, data, atoms.ids)
26
27 local_dofs(dim, i) = (1:dim) .+ dim*(i-1)
28
29 function coupling_matrix(x, dof, ::Val{dim}=Val(3)) where dim
30     x_vec = [Vec{dim}(xi) for xi in eachcol(x)]
31     ip = geometric_interpolation(dof.grid)
32     ph = PointEvalHandler(dof.grid, x_vec)
33     cc = CellCache(dof)
34
35     I = Int[]
36     J = Int[]
37     V = Float64[]
38
39     for (j, point) in enumerate(PointIterator(ph))
40         cols = local_dofs(dim, j)
41         Ferrite.reinit!(cc, point.cid)
42
43         for i in 1:getnbasefunctions(ip)
44             rows = @view cc.dofs[local_dofs(dim, i)]
45             value = Ferrite.reference_shape_value(ip, point.local_coord, i)
46
47             append!(I, rows)
48             append!(J, cols)
49             append!(V, value for _ in 1:dim)
50         end
51     end
52
53     return sparse(I, J, V, ndofs(dof), length(x))
54 end
55
56 #####
57 # Anchor Atoms #
58 #####
59
60 struct AnchorAtoms
61     atoms::AtomGroup
62     initial_pos::Matrix{Float64}
63     u::Vector{Float64}
64     G::SparseMatrixCSC{Float64, Int}
65     K::SparseMatrixCSC{Float64, Int}
66
67     function AnchorAtoms(atoms::AtomGroup, dof, anchor_stiffness)
68         initial_pos = gather(atoms, "x", Float64)
69         u = zeros(ndofs(dof))
70         G = coupling_matrix(initial_pos, dof)
71         K = G * anchor_stiffness * G'
72         return new(atoms, initial_pos, u, G, K)
73     end
74 end

```

```

75
76 AnchorAtoms(lmp::LMP, group, dof, anchor_stiffness) = AnchorAtoms(AtomGroup(lmp,
    group), dof, anchor_stiffness)
77
78 function get_anchorforces(anchor::AnchorAtoms, name)
79     forces = gather(anchor.atoms, name, Float64)
80     return anchor.K*anchor.u + anchor.G * vec(forces)
81 end
82
83 function set_displacements!(anchor::AnchorAtoms, u)
84     copyto!(anchor.u, u) # needed for `get_anchorforces`
85     new_pos = anchor.initial_pos + reshape(anchor.G' * anchor.u, (3,:))
86     scatter!(anchor.atoms, "x", new_pos)
87 end
88
89 get_embedded_stiffness(anchor::AnchorAtoms) = anchor.K
90
91 #####
92 # Fur Atoms #
93 #####
94
95 struct FurAtoms
96     atoms::AtomGroup
97     initial_pos::Matrix{Float64}
98     G::SparseMatrixCSC{Float64, Int}
99
100     function FurAtoms(atoms::AtomGroup, dof)
101         initial_pos = gather(atoms, "x", Float64)
102         G = coupling_matrix(initial_pos, dof)
103         return new(atoms, initial_pos, G)
104     end
105 end
106
107 FurAtoms(lmp::LMP, group, dof) = FurAtoms(AtomGroup(lmp, group), dof)
108
109 function set_displacements!(fur::FurAtoms, u)
110     new_pos = fur.initial_pos + reshape(fur.G' * u, (3,:))
111     scatter!(fur.atoms, "x", new_pos)
112 end

```

Listing B.11: Linearelasticity.jl.

```

1 struct Hooke
2     C::SymmetricTensor{4, 3, Float64, 36}
3 end
4
5 function Hooke(E, ν)
6     μ = 0.5 * E / (1 + ν)
7     λ = E * ν / ((1 + ν) * (1 - 2ν))
8
9     I = one(SymmetricTensor{2, 3})
10    Isym = one(SymmetricTensor{4, 3})
11
12    return Hooke(λ * I ⊗ I + 2μ * Isym)
13 end
14
15 struct LinearelasticAssembler
16     Kc::SparseMatrixCSC{Float64, Int}
17     mp::Hooke
18     dh::DofHandler
19     ah::AlphaHandler
20 end
21
22 function create_assembler(mp::Hooke, dh::DofHandler, ah::AlphaHandler)
23     Kc = allocate_matrix(dh)
24     assembler = start_assemble(Kc)
25

```

```

26 ke = element_matrix(dh)
27
28 cellvalues = cell_values(dh)
29 alphavalues = AlphaValues(ah)
30
31 for cell in CellIterator(only(dh.subdofhandlers))
32     reinit!(cellvalues, cell)
33     reinit!(alphavalues, cell)
34     fill!(ke, 0)
35
36     _assemble_element!(mp, ke, cellvalues, alphavalues)
37     assemble!(assembler, celldofs(cell), ke)
38 end
39
40 return LinearelasticAssembler(Kc, mp, dh, ah)
41 end
42
43 function _assemble_element!(mp::Hooke, ke, cellvalues, alphavalues)
44     for qp in 1:getnquadpoints(cellvalues)
45          $\alpha_{d\Omega}$  = alpha_value(alphavalues, qp) * getdetJdV(cellvalues, qp)
46         for i in 1:getnbasefunctions(cellvalues), j in 1:getnbasefunctions(
47             cellvalues)
48              $\nabla\delta_{ui}$  = shape_gradient(cellvalues, qp, i)
49              $\nabla\delta_{uj}$  = shape_gradient(cellvalues, qp, j)
50             ke[i,j] += ( $\nabla\delta_{ui}$   $\boxtimes$  mp.C  $\boxtimes$   $\nabla\delta_{uj}$ ) *  $\alpha_{d\Omega}$ 
51         end
52     end
53 end
54
55 function stiffness_matrix(fem::LinearelasticAssembler, u::AbstractVector)
56     return fem.Kc, fem.Kc * u
57 end
58
59 function compute_forces(fem::LinearelasticAssembler, u::AbstractVector)
60     return fem.Kc * u
61 end
62
63 # compute stresses at quadrature points
64 function compute_stresses(fem::LinearelasticAssembler, u::AbstractVector)
65     cellvalues = cell_values(fem.dh)
66     nqp = 8
67
68     stresses = zeros(Tensor{2,3}, nqp, getncells(fem.dh.grid))
69
70     for (cell_num, cell) in enumerate(CellIterator(fem.dh))
71         isempty(celldofs(cell)) && continue
72         reinit!(cellvalues, cell)
73
74         for qp in 1:nqp
75              $\varepsilon$  = function_symmetric_gradient(cellvalues, qp, u, celldofs(cell))
76             stresses[qp, cell_num] = fem.mp.C  $\boxtimes$   $\varepsilon$ 
77         end
78     end
79
80     return stresses
81 end

```

Listing B.12: Hyperelasticity.jl.

```

1 struct NeoHooke
2      $\mu$ ::Float64
3      $\lambda$ ::Float64
4
5     function NeoHooke(E,  $\nu$ )
6          $\mu$  = 0.5 * E / (1 +  $\nu$ )
7          $\lambda$  = E *  $\nu$  / ((1 +  $\nu$ ) * (1 - 2 $\nu$ ))
8         return new( $\mu$ ,  $\lambda$ )

```

```

9     end
10  end
11
12  struct HyperelasticAssembler{DH<:DofHandler, AH<:AlphaHandler}
13      mp::NeoHooke
14
15      dh::DH
16      ah::AH
17
18      Kc::SparseMatrixCSC{Float64, Int}
19      r::Vector{Float64}
20
21      owned_elements::Vector{Int}
22  end
23
24  function create_assembler(mm::NeoHooke, dh::DofHandler, ah::AlphaHandler)
25      Kc = allocate_matrix(dh)
26      r = system_vector(dh)
27
28      cellset = collect(only(dh.subdofhandlers).cellset)::Vector{Int}
29      owned_elements = cellset[MPI.Comm_rank(MPI.COMM_WORLD)+1:MPI.Comm_size(MPI.
30          COMM_WORLD):end]
31
32      return HyperelasticAssembler(mm, dh, ah, Kc, r, owned_elements)
33  end
34
35  function stiffness_matrix(fem::HyperelasticAssembler, displ::AbstractVector)
36      assembler = start_assemble(fem.Kc, fem.r)
37
38      ke = element_matrix(fem.dh)
39      re = element_vector(fem.dh)
40
41      cellvalues = cell_values(fem.dh)
42      alphavalues = AlphaValues(fem.ah)
43
44      for cell in CellIterator(fem.dh, fem.owned_elements)
45          reinit!(cellvalues, cell)
46          reinit!(alphavalues, cell)
47          fill!(ke, 0)
48          fill!(re, 0)
49
50          _assemble_element!(fem, ke, re, cell, cellvalues, alphavalues, displ)
51
52          assemble!(assembler, celldofs(cell), re, ke)
53      end
54
55      MPI.Allreduce!(fem.Kc.nzval, +, MPI.COMM_WORLD)
56      MPI.Allreduce!(fem.r, +, MPI.COMM_WORLD)
57
58      return fem.Kc, fem.r
59  end
60
61  function _assemble_element!(fem::HyperelasticAssembler, ke, re, cell, cellvalues
62      , alphavalues, displ)
63      for qp in 1:getnquadpoints(cellvalues)
64           $\alpha_{d\Omega}$  = alpha_value(alphavalues, qp) * getdetJdV(cellvalues, qp)
65          F = deformation_gradient(cellvalues, qp, displ, celldofs(cell))
66          C = tdot(F)
67          S,  $\partial S \partial C$  = constitutive_driver(C, fem.mp)
68          P = F · S
69          I = one(S)
70           $\partial P \partial F$  = otimesu(I, S) + 2 * otimesu(F, I)  $\square$   $\partial S \partial C$   $\square$  otimesu(F', I)
71
72          for i in 1:getnbasefunctions(cellvalues)
73               $\nabla \delta u_i$  = shape_gradient(cellvalues, qp, i)
74              re[i] +=  $\nabla \delta u_i$   $\square$  P *  $\alpha_{d\Omega}$ 
75
76               $\nabla \delta u_i \partial P \partial F$  =  $\nabla \delta u_i$   $\square$   $\partial P \partial F$ 
77              for j in 1:getnbasefunctions(cellvalues)
78                   $\nabla \delta u_j$  = shape_gradient(cellvalues, qp, j)

```

```

77         ke[i, j] += (∇δui∂P∂F ⊠ ∇δuj) * α_dΩ
78     end
79 end
80 end
81 end
82
83 function compute_stresses(fem::HyperelasticAssembler, u::AbstractVector)
84     cellvalues = cell_values(fem.dh)
85     nqp = 8
86
87     stresses = zeros(Tensor{2,3}, nqp, getncells(fem.dh.grid))
88
89     for (cell_num, cell) in enumerate(CellIterator(fem.dh))
90         isempty(celldofs(cell)) && continue
91         reinit!(cellvalues, cell)
92
93         for qp in 1:nqp
94             F = deformation_gradient(cellvalues, qp, u, celldofs(cell))
95             C = tdot(F)
96             S, _ = constitutive_driver(C, fem.mp)
97             stresses[qp, cell_num] = (F · S · F') / det(F)
98         end
99     end
100
101     return stresses
102 end
103
104 function Ψ(C, mp::NeoHooke)
105     Ic = tr(C)
106     lnJ = 0.5(log(det(C)))
107     return 0.5mp.μ * (Ic-3-2lnJ) + 0.5mp.λ * lnJ^2
108 end
109
110 function constitutive_driver(C, mp::NeoHooke)
111     ∂²Ψ∂C², ∂Ψ∂C = Tensors.hessian(y -> Ψ(y, mp), C, :all)
112     S = 2∂Ψ∂C
113     ∂S∂C = 2∂²Ψ∂C²
114     return S, ∂S∂C
115 end

```